

Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

D3.5 INDICATOR TOOLBOX FOR ASSESSING ECOSYSTEM SERVICES OF WETLANDS

24/11/2025

PARTNERS

MINISTRY OF ENVIRONMENT,
WATERS AND FORESTS

viadonau

Grant Agreement No.: 101112736
Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01
Topic: HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-02
Type of action: HORIZON Innovation Actions

D3.5 ASSESSMENT INDICATOR TOOLBOX

TOOLBOX OF EASILY APPLICABLE LOW-COST ASSESSMENT INDICATORS AND METHODS
FOR ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN WETLANDS

Work package	WP 3
Task	Task 3.2
Due date	30/11/2025
Submission date	24/11/2025
Deliverable lead	BOKU
Version	2.0
Authors	Marie Wahl (BOKU), Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU), Mihai Cristian Adamescu (UB), Viktoria Arnold (BOKU), Georgia Arhire (UB), Biljana Basarin (UNSPMF), Dušanka Cvijanović (UNSPMF), Valentin Dinu (UB), Cristina Despina (INCDDD), Eva Feldbacher (BOKU), Krisztina Gulyás (EMVIZIG), Andrej Halabuk (ILESAS), Ľuboš Halada (ILESAS), Ute Susanne Kaden (UFZ), Đurađ Milošević (FSM), Maja Novković (UNSPMF), Zorica Podračanin (UNSPMF), Tudor Racoviceanu (UB), Aleksandar Radošević (UNSPMF), Marian Radu (UB), Clara Rosenberger (BOKU), Milan Segedinac (UNSPMF), Mathias Scholz (UFZ), Bano Mehdi Schulz (BOKU), Albert Scricciu (GeoEcoMar), Barbara Stammel (KUEI), Milica Stojković Piperac (FSM), Andrei Toma (GeoEcoMar), Johanna Weidendorfer (KUEI), Martin Tschikof (BOKU)
Reviewers	Laura Coulson (BOKU) Johanna Weidendorfer (KUEI)

Abstract	<p>Wetlands provide essential ecosystem services (ES) such as habitat provisioning, climate regulation, water purification, and flood mitigation, yet they are among the most threatened ecosystems globally. This deliverable presents a comprehensive toolbox of indicators and methods tailored for European wetlands, tested in the Danube River Basin, and designed to support wetland restoration and sustainable management. The toolbox includes geospatial analyses and field measurements suitable for both experts and citizen scientists, evaluating regulating, cultural, and provisioning ES based on the CICES framework. It offers factsheets, practical recommendations, expert judgements on accuracy, costs, and required expertise, as well as detailed protocols for proper application. By testing and comparing methods, their strengths and limitations were identified, equipping users with practical tools to assess wetland resilience and multifunctionality. While not exhaustive, the toolbox serves as a valuable resource for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners, enabling targeted restoration efforts and wider participation through citizen science.</p>
Keywords	Ecosystem Services, Wetland Evaluation, Citizen Science

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	26/03/25	First Draft	Weigelhofer, G.
1.0	15/10/2025	Factsheets written and compiled	All authors
1.1	14/11/2025	Expert review	Coulson, L.; Weidendorfer J., Adamescu, C. M.
1.2	22/11/2025	Final Review by authors	All authors
2.0	24/11/2025	Final Document	Wahl, M. Weigelhofer, G. Tschikof, M.

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© Restore4Life Consortium, 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Nature of the deliverable:

Report

Dissemination Level

PU

Public, fully open, e.g. web

The (insert) Consortium is the following:

Participant number	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	UNIVERSITATEA DIN BUCURESTI	UB	RO
2	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	BOKU	AT
3	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU GEOLOGIE SI GEOECOLOGIE MARINA	GEOECOMAR	RO
4	UNIVERSITATEA DUNAREA DE JOS DIN GALATI	UGAL	RO
6	UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD FACULTY OF SCIENCES	UNSPMF	RS
8	PRIPODNO MATEMATICKI FAKULTET	FSM	RS
10	KATHOLISCHE UNIVERSITÄT EICHSTÄTT-INGOLSTADT	KUEI	DE
13	INSTITUTE OF LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY OF THE SLOVAK ACADEMY OF SCIENCES,	ILESAS	SK
17	ESZAK-MAGYARORSZAGI VIZUGYI IGAZGATOSAG	EMVIZIG	HU
27	HELMHOLZ-ZENTRUM FÜR UMWELTFORSCHUNG GMBH	UFZ	DE
28	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETAREDEZVOLTARE DELTA DUNARII	INCDDD	RO

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Wetlands provide essential ecosystem services (ES) such as habitat provisioning, climate regulation, water purification, and flood mitigation, yet they are among the most threatened ecosystems globally. Restoring wetlands is critical to preserving biodiversity and ensuring the delivery of ES in the face of environmental challenges. This deliverable addresses the need for practical, cost-effective tools to assess and monitor wetland ES, supporting targeted restoration efforts and sustainable management.

A comprehensive toolbox of indicators and methods was developed, tailored for European wetlands, and tested in the Danube River Basin to ensure broad applicability. The toolbox includes geospatial analyses and field measurements, suitable for both experts and citizen scientists, and evaluates regulating, cultural, and provisioning ES according to the CICES framework. Each method is supported by factsheets, and practical recommendations to ensure usability and reliability. Expert judgements on accuracy, required expertise, time, and costs help users to identify appropriate methods meeting their demands. For some of the methods, detailed protocols were elaborated to ensure proper application.

By testing and comparing the methods, their strengths and limitations were detected and are discussed herein. While the toolbox is not exhaustive, it equips users with practical methods to evaluate wetland resilience and multifunctionality and refers to further helpful material. This deliverable offers a resource for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners to guide wetland restoration and management, and citizen science applications enable wider participation and cost-efficient data collection.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	7
ABBREVIATIONS.....	8
1 INTRODUCTION.....	10
1.1 BACKGROUND.....	10
1.2 AIM OF THE TOOLBOX.....	10
1.3 GUIDELINE.....	11
2 OVERVIEW OF THE INDICATOR TOOLBOX.....	12
3 INDICATOR TOOLBOX.....	14
4 COMPARISON OF METHODS.....	22
4.1 HABITAT DIVERSITY.....	22
4.2 PLANT DIVERSITY.....	24
4.3 ANIMAL DIVERSITY.....	25
4.4 GLOBAL CLIMATE REGULATION.....	26
4.5 MICRO-CLIMATE REGULATION.....	27
4.6 DROUGHT MITIGATION.....	28
4.7 FLOOD MITIGATION.....	29
4.8 EROSION AND SEDIMENT TRANSPORT CONTROL.....	30
4.9 WATER PURIFICATION.....	32
4.10 SOIL QUALITY.....	33
4.11 RECREATION.....	34
4.12 RESEARCH AND EDUCATION.....	35
4.13 PLANT BIOMASS (MATERIAL).....	36
4.14 PLANT BIOMASS (FOOD/FEED).....	36
4.15 BIOMASS AND STOCKS (FOOD).....	37
4.16 PROVISION OF WATER.....	37
5 FURTHER TOOLS AND METHODS.....	38
REFERENCES.....	40
APPENDIX: FACT SHEETS.....	41

ABBREVIATIONS

ACS	Angle Count Sampling
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
AGB	Above-ground biomass
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Arable Crop Production Index
ARIES	Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability
CFI	Commercial Fishing Index
CHI	Commercial Hunting Index
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
CS	Citizen Science/Scientists
DEM / DTM	Digital Elevation / Terrain Model
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
DRB	Danube River Basin
eDNA	environmental DNA
EO Earth	Observation
ES	Ecosystem Services
EVI	Enhanced Vegetation Index
EWM	European Wetland Map
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GHG	Greenhouse Gas(es)
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HRUs	Hydrological Response Units
InVEST	Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs
LCLU	Land Cover / Land Use

LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
NDMI	Normalized Difference Moisture Index
PBI	Plant Biomass Index
RAWES	Ramsar Rapid Assessment of Wetland Ecosystem Services
RESI	River Ecosystem Service Index
RGB	Red-Green-Blue
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
SWAT	Soil and Water Assessment Tool
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
TN	Total Nitrogen
TP	Total Phosphorus
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WAVI	Water Adjusted Vegetation Index
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WQI	Water Quality Index

1 INTRODUCTION

Restore4Life (Restoration of wetland complexes as life supporting systems in the Danube Basin, project 101112736) is a Horizon Europe-funded project that supports the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”. The Mission aims to protect and restore the health of our aquatic systems through research and innovation, citizen engagement, and blue investments. The Mission’s new approach treats the ocean and other waterbodies as one system and plays a key role in achieving climate neutrality and restoring nature.

Restore4Life aims to develop a “Restore4Life Wetland Restoration Decision Support System” at the Danube Basin level. This service is based on a shared vision for wetland restoration, including co-creation and co-development of tools that will enable local stakeholders to be actively involved in restoration works and help local businesses adopt new strategies through nature-based solutions.

1.1 BACKGROUND

Located at a dynamic interface between aquatic and terrestrial environments, wetlands provide a disproportionately high diversity of ecosystem services (ES). These include habitat provisioning, climate regulation, water purification, nutrient and sediment retention, flood mitigation, recreation, and food production [1], [2]. Despite their high ecological and socio-economic value, wetlands are among the most threatened ecosystems worldwide, having lost large areas due to land-use changes, drainage, pollution, and hydrological alteration [3], [4]. Restoration of wetland systems aims to recover and enhance ecological functions and ES, ensuring that these systems continue to support biodiversity, human well-being, and climate resilience. Restoration should not simply attempt to recreate historical ecosystem states. Instead, restoration should aim to design and manage wetland systems to be multifunctional, resilient, and future-oriented, capable of maintaining ecosystem service delivery under changing conditions [5], [6]. Therefore, a comprehensive and transparent assessment of wetland ES is essential – not only to evaluate the current state but to define forward-facing restoration objectives and monitor trajectories of service provision and resilience over time.

1.2 AIM OF THE TOOLBOX

This toolbox provides a comprehensive selection of **cost-effective, publicly accessible, and widely applicable user-friendly methods and indicators for monitoring and assessing ES** in European wetlands. The methods cover a wide range of ES and include **geospatial analyses** and **field measurements** for both researchers and citizen scientists.

All methods have been tested by Restore4Life partners in the Danube River Basin to optimize their replicability across European wetland systems. Based on the experiences of the testers, the toolbox provides information on the method’s potential, limitations, applicability, and

suitability for citizen science, and offers recommendations for improvements. Furthermore, the toolbox includes links to detailed working protocols where available. For specific methods, especially those involving citizen scientists (CS), we have developed and tested protocols that can be downloaded from Zenodo and adapted to the requirements of the specific wetland restoration project.

It should be noted that the toolbox **does not include** detailed scientific methods and standard operational protocols. Laboratory procedures are generally excluded, as they are widely available and depend on the equipment and resources of individual laboratories. Additionally, such methods are often expensive and typically reserved for professionals in the field. Finally, it should be mentioned that this toolbox does not cover methods for assessing *carbon sequestration*, as these will be covered in a separate manual (Deliverable 3.6 – Manual for Carbon Sequestration Monitoring). In this deliverable, only methods for assessing *carbon stocks* are provided.

1.3 GUIDELINE

The toolbox allows users to select a suitable method for a specific indicator, based on the available infrastructure, staff, expertise, and funding. For some of the methods, detailed protocols were elaborated to ensure proper application. For each indicator, geospatial analyses and field measurements are offered.

The toolbox is organized in a systematic, tabular manner to help users easily find suitable approaches. Each method is linked to a concise fact sheet that provides a short method description, the method's advantages and limitations, experts' judgments on its applicability, and recommendations. Experts' judgments include an evaluation of the method's expected accuracy, required expertise, time demands, and estimated costs. Recommendations offer additional guidance on the method's application or other practical considerations.

For each specific ES type, the individual indicators and methods are compared and discussed based on our experience from the method testing (see chapter 4: COMPARISON OF METHODS). This section provides practical insights into the applicability and comparability of different methods, enabling users to make informed decisions.

2 OVERVIEW OF THE INDICATOR TOOLBOX

STRUCTURE

The toolbox is divided into three main sections, corresponding to the ES sections defined by the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) classification: **regulating and maintenance** services, **cultural** services, and **provisioning** services. The hierarchical structure of CICES (Section > Division > Group > Class > Type) serves as a reference classification of ES, enabling comparisons across different ES classification systems [7].

Within each section, several tables are provided, organized by CICES groups. Each table contains detailed information about the following:

TABLE 1: ORGANIZATION OF THE TOOLBOX FOR EACH ES-SECTION

ES-Classes	Name of the ecosystem service class or classes within the CICES group
ES-Type	Name of the specific ecosystem service
Spatial scale	Geospatial analysis OR field measurement
Indicator (Units)	Name of the indicator being measured, its units, and its desired direction of change due to restoration
Method	Name of the method, protocol availability, and suitability for citizen scientists.
Judgment	Level of expected accuracy of the tested method, necessary expertise, time requirements, and estimated costs.
ID	Unique identifier linking to detailed fact sheets and protocols.

ICONS FOR RESTORATION IMPACTS

The listed quantitative indicators may increase or decrease as a result of the restoration efforts. To guide restoration works and evaluate their success, the following table shows the icons representing the desired direction of indicator change:

TABLE 2: DESIRED IMPACTS OF RESTORATION WORKS ON INDICATORS

Symbol	Meaning
	Increase after restoration
	Decrease after restoration
	Increase and/or decrease after restoration

ICONS FOR EXPERT JUDGEMENT

An expert judgment is provided for each tested method, covering the method's expected level of accuracy, required expertise, time needed per assessment, and estimated costs. An icon represents each of these four aspects, with the number of icons indicating the level of demand: 1 icon signifies low, 2 icons medium, and 3 icons high demand. To ensure consistent judgement, approximate descriptions of their meaning have been provided. The following table lists the icons and their meaning:

TABLE 3: EXPERT JUDGEMENT OF THE METHODS' PERFORMANCE ACCORDING TO ACCURACY, NECESSARY EXPERTISE, TIME AND COSTS

Category	Symbol	Meaning
Accuracy of measurement		Low accuracy (>75% deviation/misclassified)
		Medium accuracy (50–75% deviation/misclassified)
		High accuracy (<25% deviation/misclassified)
Necessary expertise/training		No former training necessary
		Basic training necessary
		More intensive training necessary
Time needed		Minutes
		Hours
		Days
Estimated costs	€	Free or with standard equipment (laptop, household items)
	€ €	<200€
	€ € €	>200€

ICONS FOR ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

For a selection of methods, icons are provided to indicate whether a detailed protocol is publicly available and whether the method is suitable for citizen scientists:

TABLE 4: ADDITIONAL INFORMATION AND MATERIAL

Symbol	Meaning
	Link to detailed protocol available in the fact sheet under "sources"
	Suitable for Citizen Scientists

3 INDICATOR TOOLBOX

SECTION REGULATION & MAINTENANCE (CICES V5.1)

ES-Group: Life cycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool expression

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Maintaining nursery populations* and habitats Pest and disease control (including invasive species)	Habitat diversity	Geospatial analysis	Extent of typical wetland habitats (ha) ↗	Habitat provisioning index (IDES) 📄		RGH1 p.42
				Habitat/Species distribution modelling		RHG2 p.44
				Image classification (habitat mapping) 📄		RHG3 p.46
			Habitat configuration and connectivity ↗	Analysis of spatial patterns and networks		RHG4 p.48
	Field measurement	Type, hydro-morphology, and status of water bodies ↻	Water body mapping 📄 🏗️		RHF1b p.49	

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Maintaining nursery populations* and habitats	Plant diversity	Geospatial analysis	Presence of typical wetland species (n) €	RPG2 p.50		
Presence of invasive species (n)						
Pest and disease control (including invasive species)		Field measurement	Presence of typical wetland plant species (n) €	RPF1b p.52		
			Presence of invasive species (n)			

*Testing indicators of **animal diversity** proved that experts are required to identify mobile animals in the field.

ES-Group: Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Atmospheric composition and conditions	Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gases	Geospatial analysis	Total Carbon stock and flux (tC/ha) €	RCG1 p.53		
				Spectral indices €€€	RCG2 p.54	
				Earth observation & models	 €	RCG3 p.55

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Atmospheric composition and conditions	Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gases	Field measurement	Carbon in plant biomass (tC/ha) ↗	Tree inventory	🔍🔍🔍 🕒🕒 €	<u>RCF1</u> p.57
				Tree height and circumference, tree biomass 📄 🌳	🔍🔍 💡💡 🕒 €	<u>RCF2</u> p.58
				Harvesting herbaceous biomass 🌳	🔍 💡 🕒 €	<u>RCF3</u> p.60
				Herbaceous biomass with the PhytoCalc method	🔍🔍🔍 💡💡💡 🕒🕒 €	<u>RCF4</u> p.61
			Carbon in soils (tC/ha) ↗	Carbon in shallow organic layer 📄 🌳	💡💡 🕒 €€	<u>RCF4a</u> p.62
				Carbon in deep organic layer 📄 🌳	🔍🔍 💡💡 🕒🕒 €€	<u>RCF4b</u> p.63
			Micro- and regional climate regulation	Geospatial analysis	Regional temperature extremes ↘	Climpact heat wave index

ES-Group: Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Control of erosion rates Buffering and attenuation of mass movement Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control)	Drought mitigation	Geospatial analysis	Drought events (frequency, duration, amplitude) ↘	LSTM AI model		<u>RDG2</u> p.65
				SWAT+ model		<u>RDG3</u> p.67
	Fire protection	Field measurement	Soil moisture (%) ↗	Data loggers		<u>RDF1</u> p.69
				Soil moisture measurements	<u>RCF4a</u> p.62	
	Flood mitigation	Geospatial analysis	Water level (m) ↗	Water level measurements (CrowdWater app)	<u>RDF4</u> p.70	
				Water surface area (ha) ↗	Spectral indices (NDWI)	
	Flood mitigation	Geospatial analysis	Floodplain volume (m ³) ↗	Flood risk regulation index (IDES)	<u>RFG4</u> p.73	

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Control of erosion rates	Flood mitigation	Field measurement	Water volume (m ³)	<u>RFG3</u> p.75		
Buffering and attenuation of mass movement	Erosion and sediment transport control	Geospatial analysis	Sediment surface (ha)	<u>REG1</u> p.76		
Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control)			Sediment volume (m ³)	<u>REG2</u> p.78		
		Field measurement	Sediment volume (m ³)	<u>REF1</u> p.80		

ES-Group: Mediation of wastes or toxic substances, Regulation of water condition and soil quality

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Bio-remediation; filtration, sequestration, storage, accumulation Regulation of the chemical condition of freshwaters	Water purification	Geospatial analysis	Nutrient retention (kg/ha) ↗	Nutrient retention index (IDES) 📄	💡💡💡 🕒🕒 €	<u>RWG2</u> p.82
		Field measurement	Water quality (nutrients, dissolved oxygen, algae) ↗	Water quality index	💡💡💡 🕒🕒🕒 €€€	<u>RWF1</u> p.83
				Field test kits 📄 🌱🌱🌱	💡💡 🕒 €€	<u>RWF3</u> p.85
Decomposition and fixing processes and their effect on soil quality	Improvement of soil quality Distribution of wetland soils	Field measurement	Extent and depth of wetland/peatland soils ↗	Soil structure, water retention capacity, organic matter content 📄 🌱🌱🌱	💡💡 🕒 €€	<u>RCF4a</u> p.62
				Peat structure, water retention capacity, organic matter content 📄 🌱🌱🌱	🕒🕒 💡💡 €€	<u>RCF4b</u> p.63

SECTION CULTURAL (CICES V5.1)

ES-Group: Physical and experiential interactions with natural environment (direct interaction) (CICES)

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Characteristics of living systems that enable activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment	Recreation	Field measurement	Infrastructure quality and quantity regarding recreation opportunities ↗	Infrastructure analysis €	<u>CRF1</u> p.86	

ES-Group: Intellectual and representative interactions with natural environment (direct interaction) (CICES)

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Characteristics of living systems that enable scientific investigations, education and training	Research and education	Field measurement	Number and configuration of educational trails and information boards ↗	Assessment of educational trails (CS) €	<u>CEF1</u> p.87	

SECTION PROVISIONING (CICES V5.1)

ES-Group: Cultivated terrestrial plants for nutrition, materials or energy (CICES)

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Fibres and other materials from (cultivated) plants for direct use or processing	Biomass (material)*	Geospatial analysis	Reed area (ha) €	<u>RBG2</u> p.88		
	*Forest biomass, as an indicator for timber and firewood production, can be assessed using the indicators of "Global Climate Regulation" ("Total Carbon stock and flux (tC/ha)" and "Carbon in plant biomass (tC/ha)"; chapter 4.4), also calculating wood biomass at one stage.					
Cultivated terrestrial plants (including fungi, algae) grown for nutritional purposes	Biomass (food/feed)	Geospatial analysis	Agricultural area (ha) and yield potential €	<u>PBG1</u> p.89		

Group: (Reared) aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy (CICES)

ES- Classes	ES-Type	Spatial Scale	Indicator (Units)	Method	Judgment	ID
Animals (reared by in-situ aquaculture) for nutritional purposes	Biomass and stocks (food)	Geospatial analysis	Fishing /hunting yields and quotas €	<u>PAG1</u> p.90		

ES-Group: Surface water used for nutrition, materials or energy (CICES)

The area, volume, and quality of surface water available for various uses can be assessed using indicators of the ES "drought mitigation" (chapter 4.6), "flood mitigation" (chapter 4.7), and "water purification" (chapter 4.9).

4 COMPARISON OF METHODS

In this chapter, the individual indicators and methods for assessing ES are discussed in detail and compared. A qualitative discussion is provided for each ES-class focusing on which methods are best applicable under specific conditions, such as data availability, analysis scale, required expertise, and intended use. The chapter also incorporates practical experiences and insights gained during the development of the toolbox, offering recommendations to help users select the most suitable method. By highlighting the strengths, limitations, and contexts of use for each approach, this chapter aims to support informed decision-making and effective assessment of ES.

4.1 HABITAT DIVERSITY

The variety of habitats within wetlands is fundamental for sustaining their ecological health, resilience, and functionality. A diverse range of habitats foster biodiversity, strengthens ecosystem processes, and enhances the wetlands' ability to withstand environmental pressures. Beyond these ecological benefits, diverse habitats contribute to the cultural, aesthetic, and recreational value of wetlands, enriching human experiences and connections to nature. Protecting and restoring habitat diversity is essential for maintaining the ecological balance of wetlands and ensuring their long-term sustainability. Particular focus should be placed on the conservation of habitats listed in Annex I of the Habitats Directive, as they are of community interest.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

The assessment of habitat diversity through geospatial analyses can be done with various approaches, including index calculations, modelling, image classification techniques, and metrics calculations. These methods generally achieve medium to high accuracy and usually require advanced training.

Index calculations are based on the IDES tool [8] and are designed for application in the Danube River Basin. These indices rely on freely available data and are particularly effective for evaluating floodplain and river habitats at larger scales. However, their applicability is limited to floodplains, and they cannot assess the effects of local restoration measures, which restricts their use in site-specific studies.

Through **habitat modelling**, the distribution of wetland habitats can be predicted, and habitat suitability maps can be generated. The required datasets and user-friendly software are freely available. The accuracy of the model's output depends heavily on the quality of the input data. The results require expert interpretation and should be validated with field observations, as the data may be spatially biased. This method can be applied to cover large areas and help identify regions at risk or requiring management action.

Habitat mapping using **image classification** techniques, such as UAV-based photogrammetry, is an effective method for assessing the presence and characteristics of aquatic vegetation and habitats. This approach provides high-resolution results and is adaptable to areas with changing characteristics, which makes it suitable for monitoring temporal changes. Although this method is cost-effective, the initial investment in UAV equipment is high. Additionally, this method requires a high level of expertise for data acquisition and processing, as well as significant data storage capacity for large-scale assessments. Ground-truthing is essential for validating the results and ensuring accuracy.

Another valuable approach is the calculation of **metrics for habitat configuration and connectivity**. Several freely accessible, open-source R packages are available for analysing landscape configuration and connectivity at various scales, including river networks. However, users require experience in R programming, and interpretation of the results may be complex.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Habitat diversity can be assessed through **field-based habitat mapping**. In this toolbox, we focused on mapping wetland water bodies. The available protocol offers medium accuracy due to the coarse resolution of the collected data and does not require prior training, making it user-friendly and suitable for citizen scientists (CS). Water bodies are mapped by recording key hydro-morphological and riparian characteristics, as well as their usage and water quality. Repeating the survey on the same water body over time allows identification of water level fluctuations and intermittency. Field assessments by CS may be limited in areas with dense vegetation or in remote and/or protected locations where access is restricted.

More sophisticated waterbody mapping, as well as mapping of terrestrial habitats, requires expertise and is therefore not included in the toolbox.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses are ideal for large-scale assessments, as most methods can cover extensive areas efficiently. However, the quality of the results depends on the input data, and each method has its own specific focus or area of application, which may limit its versatility. Additionally, all these methods require a high level of expertise.

Geospatial tools supply an overarching view of habitat distribution, landscape structure, and large-scale patterns that would be impossible to capture solely through fieldwork. At the same time, field measurements validate and enrich remote observations by providing accurate, ground-level information on species composition, microhabitat conditions, and ecological processes that satellites or models may overlook. While these methods are more labour-intensive, they can yield valuable data on specific habitat characteristics. However, their application is limited to smaller areas and may be restricted in remote or protected locations.

By combining geospatial analyses with field measurements, users can gain complementary insights into habitat diversity as a solid base for effective management and conservation strategies. Ultimately, the synergy of these methods supports more effective, evidence-based decision-making—ensuring that conservation strategies are both **scalable and sensitive** to the nuances of individual ecosystems.

4.2 PLANT DIVERSITY

Preserving a rich diversity of wetland-specific plants while controlling invasive species is crucial for safeguarding the health, functionality, and resilience of wetland ecosystems. A high diversity of native plants contributes to the stability and productivity of these ecosystems, supporting overall biodiversity. Special attention should be given to the conservation status of species of community interest, such as those listed in Annex II and Annex IV of the Habitats Directive. At the same time, preventing and managing invasive species is crucial for protecting wetlands from degradation and maintaining ecological balance.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

The diversity of plant species, including both typical wetland and invasive species, can be assessed using **database queries**. Platforms like iNaturalist¹ and databases like GBIF² provide free, open-access data to the global community, offering valuable and ever-growing information on global species diversity. Assessing plant diversity for a specific wetland can be performed by both experts and citizen scientists but requires basic training. However, database queries have limitations. The lack of standardized sampling methods and the scarcity of systematic surveys can affect data reliability. Additionally, participants on platforms like iNaturalist may favour visible or charismatic species, introducing observation bias. Geographical data bias is another concern, as more data is available for highly frequented areas (especially along paths) than for remote regions. Despite these limitations, database queries are a valid starting point for assessing plant diversity in wetlands, but they should be complemented with field assessments to ensure data validation and completeness.

Plant species can also be assessed through **image classification** using remote sensing data. While this method is a valuable tool for large-scale assessments at the habitat type level (chapter 4.1.1), it requires significant expertise to function at the species level and is thus not further elaborated in this toolbox.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS SCIENCE

Citizen scientists (CS) can play a valuable role in assessing plant diversity in wetland systems after basic training. With freely available identification apps like Flora Incognita [9],

¹ available from <https://www.inaturalist.org>

² available from: <https://www.gbif.org>

Pl@ntNet³, and iNaturalist, CS can conduct field assessments to quickly identify woody and non-woody plants, including native and invasive species. This method is not destructive and incurs no material costs, making it environmentally friendly and cost-effective. The accuracy of the data depends on the CS training, the capabilities of the apps, and the quality of the camera used to capture images. Individual errors in species identifications are counterbalanced by the large dataset potentially available. Even though the method itself is straightforward, there are limitations. Some identification apps require an internet connection to function, which may not be available in remote wetland areas. Additionally, access to sensitive and protected areas is often restricted for CS, limiting data collection to along accessible paths. One advantage of involving CS in plant diversity assessments lies in their educational value and awareness raising. For accurate data, especially of highly protected species, experts are needed. However, CS data can complement professional plant diversity assessments.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses are particularly useful for covering large areas, but they are prone to geographical and observation biases, such as overrepresentation of highly frequented areas or charismatic species. In contrast, field measurements provide accurate and detailed data, especially when conducted by experts, but are often spatially restricted. By combining geospatial analyses with field measurements, users can achieve a more comprehensive and reliable assessment of plant diversity in wetlands.

4.3 ANIMAL DIVERSITY

Assessing animal diversity in wetland ecosystems requires specialized approaches and is not feasible through geospatial analyses. Monitoring the presence of typical wetland species, invasive species, and red-list species is best conducted by specialists, as accurate identification can be challenging and improper handling may disturb sensitive species or expose them to additional risks. For red-list species, their locations should be shared only with trusted conservation groups or officials to ensure their protection. While CS can contribute to biodiversity monitoring using animal identification apps, these activities have high educational but low scientific value. Our tests showed that even trained CS (except non-professional experts such as bird watchers) lack the experience to determine the right time, location, and method for finding and identifying mobile animal species. However, for selected animal species, data queries could be conducted, similar to the fact sheet: RPG2. Whereas for charismatic organism groups, such as birds, rather credible occurrence data are provided by hobby-ornithologists, for aquatic and highly mobile organisms, like fish, such queries are less suitable. For scientists, advanced techniques such as environmental DNA (eDNA) sampling offer a non-invasive, accurate approach to detecting species presence through

³ available from: <https://identify.plantnet.org/>

genetic material in water, soil, or sediment, making it particularly valuable for monitoring elusive or rare species without disturbing their habitats.

4.4 GLOBAL CLIMATE REGULATION

Wetlands, especially peatlands, are among the most effective natural systems for storing and sequestering organic carbon, making them crucial for regulating the global climate. Quantifying organic carbon stocks in plant biomass and soils is essential for understanding how wetlands mitigate climate change and maintain ecosystem health.

This toolbox offers a variety of methods for determining wetland organic carbon stocks, while carbon sequestration will be addressed in a separate manual (Deliverable 3.6.)

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

Estimating carbon stocks through geospatial analyses demonstrates high accuracy. Basic training is sufficient for using tools such as the InVEST[®] model and single Earth Observation (EO) datasets. However, advanced training is necessary for estimating carbon stocks by developing models that integrate multiple remote sensing datasets.

One of the key advantages of geospatial analyses is that the required data are freely available and often have wide, typically global, coverage. Additionally, these methods are well-suited for assessing carbon stocks over extended periods, provided that the necessary data are available. It is important to note that these methods primarily focus on above-ground carbon stocks, as below-ground carbon cannot be simply assessed using remote sensing techniques. There are also notable limitations. Proficiency in handling EO data is essential, making these methods less accessible to non-experts. Furthermore, carbon stock assessments are based on biomass estimates, which require careful calibration and interpretation to avoid misrepresentation. The spatial resolution of the data may be too coarse for analysing small areas, limiting its applicability in localized studies.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Field measurements include methods for assessing **carbon stocks in above- and below-ground (e.g. in tree and herbaceous biomass and soils)**. The procedures and protocols in this toolbox are suitable for both scientists and CS, with scientists achieving higher data accuracy, especially when using professional tools. However, **well-trained CS** can deliver reasonable carbon stock estimates at relatively low costs, particularly for above-ground estimates. However, assessing **soil carbon stocks** is only partially suitable for CS, as determining soil organic content requires burning samples at high temperatures. However, CS can significantly contribute by assessing soil structure and profiles, taking soil samples, and sending them to a laboratory. Since soil or peat samples must be extracted, these methods may not be feasible for CS in protected or sensitive areas. Recommendations for improving data quality and reducing errors are provided in the protocols.

For assessing carbon stocks in forests, the most accurate expert approach involves **tree inventories**, which rely on datasets compiled by professionals. While the carbon stock estimates for individual trees can be highly accurate, they depend on the proficiency of the data collector and the quality of data processing.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses are particularly well-suited for assessing carbon stocks over large areas, offering wide coverage through open-access data and open-source software. These methods are cost-effective and particularly useful for regional studies where broad-scale assessments are of interest. In contrast, field measurements are localized and typically cover smaller areas, making them suitable for CS involvement. CS can contribute significantly to site-specific studies, especially in homogeneous areas where sampling decisions are straightforward.

The accuracy of geospatial analyses depends on the quality of remote sensing and calibration data, the resolution of the imagery, and the models used for carbon stock estimation. Ground-truthing with field measurements is highly recommended to validate and improve the accuracy of geospatial analysis. Additionally, field measurements can also assess below-ground carbon stocks, thus providing a complete picture of the most significant organic carbon stocks in wetlands. A direct comparison with forestry inventories (as a reference) in both an implementation and a monitoring site revealed that, if applied correctly, CS estimates were in a close range, whereas InVEST and satellite-derived estimates greatly over- and underestimated carbon stocks.

4.5 MICRO-CLIMATE REGULATION

Wetland ecosystems play a critical role in regulating local temperature, humidity, and atmospheric conditions, creating stable environments that benefit both biodiversity and human communities. This regulatory function is essential for maintaining environmental stability, supporting ecosystems, and mitigating the impacts of climate change.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

The **Climpact heat wave index** can be used to assess regional climate extremes. It is freely available as an R package or via an online platform. The tool is relevant for practical decision-making across several sectors, including agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and health. Climpact is user-friendly, requiring only basic training, and primarily relies on freely available data, such as daily temperature and precipitation records. One of the key advantages of Climpact is its suitability for long-term climate trend analyses and regional and local climate assessments. However, data accuracy is medium, depending on the quality of historical meteorological data used as input.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Key environmental variables can be monitored with parameter-specific sensors, such as air temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and evapotranspiration. These measurements provide detailed, site-specific data over time on how wetlands influence local micro-climates. These techniques are well-established in the scientific community and are therefore not included in the toolbox. As meteorological measurements require standardized equipment and data are often freely available from close-by monitoring stations, we do not recommend conducting measurements with CS. For educational purposes, however, measuring differences in atmospheric temperature between different habitat types (e.g. floodplain forest vs. cropland) can illustrate the micro-climate regulation function of wetlands.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses are ideal for large-scale assessments, allowing users to evaluate long-term climate trends across extensive areas. The methods rely on freely available or remotely sensed data, but their accuracy depends heavily on the quality of the input datasets. Geospatial approaches require advanced expertise in data processing and analysis. These methods provide a broad overview of climate trends at the landscape scale, offering valuable insights into the role of wetlands in regional and global climate regulation.

Field measurements involve monitoring key environmental variables using specialized equipment. These methods are particularly valuable for long-term studies, as they can capture temporal variations and provide detailed insights into local micro-climate processes. Field measurements can complement geospatial analyses by providing detailed, localized data that help validate and refine large-scale assessments.

4.6 DROUGHT MITIGATION

A drought is defined as “drier than normal conditions” and has to be assessed in relation to the average water availability at a given season and location. Drought mitigation can be estimated using indicators such as drought frequency, soil moisture, and water levels within restored areas. By reducing the frequency, duration, or amplitude of drought events, and by increasing soil moisture and raising water levels, wetland ecosystems become more resilient to climate change, biodiversity loss, and fire hazards.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

The assessment of drought through geospatial analyses can be done with models, like **LSTM (long short-term memory) AI model** or **SWAT+** (Soil and Water Assessment Tool). These models are freely available, open-source, and have a high accuracy, provided the input data is of high quality. The models can be used for large-scale assessments and temporal analysis. The LSTM model is well-suited for peatland monitoring and similar ecosystems, and the

SWAT+ model is suitable for assessing the quality and quantity of surface water and groundwater.

A key limitation of these models is their time-consuming nature due to initial data preparation, calibration, and model training. Additionally, proficiency in Python programming, data science, and machine learning is needed for the LSTM model.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Field measurements include long-term monitoring of soil moisture and surface water levels. Soil moisture can be measured using **moisture data loggers**. Data loggers are affordable, easy to install, and provide continuous, high-accuracy monitoring along hydrological gradients. Although the **measurement of soil moisture** by CS is simple, it can only provide snapshots of the current situation and is heavily influenced by the weather. However, CS data can fill data gaps from areas where no loggers are installed.

Surface water levels are measured at **gauging stations**, providing long-term high-frequency water-level data for hydrological modelling. In publicly accessible areas, where installing a gauging station is not possible, such as small backwaters and ponds, CS can provide valuable background information on water level fluctuations and intermittency by taking pictures and/or using the **CrowdWater app**⁴.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses are highly effective for large-scale and long-term assessments, offering high accuracy when calibrated with quality input data. Models like LSTM and SWAT+ are particularly valuable for forecasting drought risks under different (climate) scenarios and analysing historical trends. Field monitoring methods with loggers provide localized, high-resolution data critical for ground-truthing geospatial models. While data loggers enable continuous temporal monitoring, manual sampling methods are labour-intensive and reflect conditions at specific points in time. However, field measurements by CS can fill data gaps in areas without loggers, serve as controls for logger data, and raise people's awareness of the most significant feature of wetlands, the various permanent and temporary water bodies. The combination of geospatial analyses and field measurements ensures both broad-scale insights and fine-scale accuracy.

4.7 FLOOD MITIGATION

Wetlands can store excess water, reducing the risk and severity of flooding in surrounding areas. They protect human communities, infrastructure, and agricultural lands from flood damage while preventing soil erosion and improving water quality by trapping sediments and pollutants.

⁴ available from <https://crowdwater.ch/>

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

Water surface area and floodplain volume can be assessed using geospatial analyses. These methods are expected to have medium accuracy and require experts. Water surface area can be measured using spectral indices, such as the **Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)**. This approach is straightforward, robust, widely used, and user-friendly, with the required data freely available online. However, its accuracy can be affected by cloud cover, dense vegetation, and other landscape features that interfere with spectral data quality.

To assess floodplain storage capacity, the **flood risk regulation index** can be applied. Developed for the IDES tool [8], this index is based on open-access data and considers water volume capacity and flow velocity reduction as key indicators. It can be applied to both floodplains and rivers but is not suitable for assessing small-scale restoration measures. The index should be used only for ES evaluations, not for flood risk management purposes.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Field-based assessments of a water body's volume can be conducted using **bathymetric surveys**. This method measures and maps the depth and terrain of riverbeds or lake bottoms, providing data that can also be used to determine discharge. Water volume and hydrology are key indicators of a water body's storage capacity, which is critical for flood mitigation. Bathymetric mapping using an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler is highly accurate and delivers a range of hydrological data, making it valuable for ground-truthing geospatial analyses. However, this method is costly due to the need for high-end equipment and is also labour-intensive, requiring specialized expertise to perform effectively, and therefore not suitable for CS.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses and field measurements can both assess water volume, a key indicator for flood mitigation, but differ significantly in scale, cost, accuracy, and labour requirements. Geospatial analyses are ideal for large-scale assessments, offering insights into floodplain dynamics and water volume across extensive areas. Field measurements provide highly accurate, site-specific data, making them valuable for small-scale assessments of localized flood mitigation measures. These methods are labour-intensive and require high-end equipment, resulting in higher costs and the need for specialized expertise.

4.8 EROSION AND SEDIMENT TRANSPORT CONTROL

Excessive erosion and sediment transport can degrade wetland habitats, disrupt hydrological processes, and reduce water quality, ultimately threatening biodiversity and the ecosystem's ability to sustain itself. Managing sediment erosion and transportation can ensure the long-term health and sustainability of wetlands.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

Geospatial analyses for controlling erosion and sediment transport include methods for assessing sediment area and sediment volume, often **using LiDAR sensors and/or satellite imagery**. These methods are highly accurate due to high spatial resolution, can be easily repeated, and are non-invasive. They are particularly well-suited for large areas and inaccessible, sensitive, or dynamic floodplain systems. Geospatial methods can assess changes in sediment volume and area over long periods, making them ideal for monitoring sediment dynamics.

The limitations of geospatial analyses include their high costs, particularly for LiDAR-based assessments, due to expensive equipment, high operational costs, and the storage of large amounts of high-resolution data. Furthermore, these methods require substantial expertise in data acquisition and processing. Finally, remote sensing data may be affected by external factors such as weather conditions or water level fluctuations, which can reduce accuracy. Validation with field measurements is often necessary to ensure reliability, especially when using remote sensing techniques to assess sediment volume.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Sediment volume can be assessed directly in the field using **sediment traps or cores**. CS can also apply these methods with basic training. Both methods are highly accurate and suitable for small- to medium-scale water bodies. They can be used for both short- and long-term assessments and for ground-truthing remote sensing methods, enhancing the accuracy of geospatial analyses.

However, these field methods have certain limitations. Access to remote areas can pose logistical challenges, and sediment traps need regular maintenance to ensure reliable data collection. Sediment extractions with cores require careful handling to avoid sample disturbance.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Geospatial analyses are well-suited for large-scale and long-term assessments, providing high-resolution, accurate data across extensive areas. However, geospatial analyses require validation through field measurements, which provide localized high-accuracy data at small to medium spatial scales. On the other hand, field measurements are labour-intensive. While CS can support data acquisition, these methods are best performed by experts due to the technical expertise required.

Together, geospatial analyses and field measurements provide a comprehensive understanding of erosion and sediment transport. Combining these approaches ensures robust, reliable results, supporting effective management and restoration measures.

4.9 WATER PURIFICATION

The water purification potential of wetland ecosystems is crucial for maintaining water quality, protecting biodiversity, and ensuring the availability of clean water for both human and ecological needs.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

Nutrient retention capacities in wetlands can be evaluated using geospatial analyses. One such method is the **index calculation for nitrogen and phosphorus retention**, developed for the IDES tool [8], which assesses the self-purification performance of river-floodplain sections. The index calculation uses openly accessible data and offers medium accuracy, depending on the quality and availability of the input data. Although designed for the Danube River Basin, this method can be adapted to other regions, provided that equivalent datasets are available. Despite its advantages, this method has some limitations. It is both labour- and time-intensive and requires advanced training in data management and analysis.

An alternative not tested in Restore4Life is the use of **spectral indices** to measure chlorophyll-a concentrations as an indicator for eutrophication (e.g., [10]). This method can be particularly useful for monitoring temporal variations in aquatic systems but requires validation through field measurements.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

For water analyses, various established protocols are used by different laboratories. Achieving high-quality results requires assessing multiple parameters, which, in turn, incurs high costs for equipment, labour, and materials. These methods also require high levels of expertise. Repeated measurements over time and across different locations can help track changes in water quality. Our toolbox offers guidance on **calculations of water quality indices (WQI)** and the maximum permissible concentrations for the measured parameters.

We have also tested **CS approaches** for assessing the water quality of rivers in various wetlands but cannot generally recommend it except for small groups of well-trained, well-equipped, and supervised CS or for educational purposes (see fact sheets and protocols). Wetland water bodies are often shallow, with heavily vegetated muddy shorelines, making it difficult to collect water samples without resuspending sediments. Water samples from organic-rich or highly productive water bodies, typical of wetlands, would need filtration before nutrient analysis. Even simple water colour determinations (brown, green, no colour) proved difficult for CS with basic training. However, combining simple water quality assessments with CS water body mapping (chapter 4.1) may yield valuable results on the state of the water body and be of high educational value.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Water quality assessments require both frequent field sampling over time to generate highly accurate, water-body-specific data, and geospatial analyses for large-scale assessments. CS can help reduce costs and workload and contribute with data on a coarse analytical scale but need intensive training and supervision.

4.10 SOIL QUALITY

Healthy wetland soils play a critical role in carbon storage, water purification, climate regulation, nutrient cycling, and habitat provision.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

In general, remote sensing methods can provide proxies for soil quality such as soil moisture, organic carbon content, and vegetation cover. Geospatial methods for assessing soil quality have been developed for the agricultural sector, but their application in wetland ecosystems is still an emerging area of research. Thus, we did not include them in the toolbox.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Soil quality methods include assessing the depth of the organic layer, texture, colour, soil type, moisture content, carbon content, and chemical properties, such as pH and nutrient concentrations. The provided methods are also suited for CS but require thorough training, including how CS can select representative sampling sites. While CS can estimate some soil parameters directly in the field with sufficient data quality, determining soil organic carbon content and nutrient concentrations requires lab analyses. The toolbox includes protocols for areas with shallow organic soil layers, such as in floodplain forests and meadows, and peatlands. Field sampling is labour-intensive and may be limited by the accessibility of the study sites, particularly in protected, sensitive, or remote areas.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

The assessment of soil quality can be approached through geospatial analyses and field measurements, each offering unique advantages and limitations. While geospatial analyses are promising for large-scale and temporal assessments, they are not covered in this toolbox. These methods rely on remote sensing data, such as soil moisture and vegetation cover, but their accuracy depends heavily on ground truthing through field measurements, highlighting the importance of integrating both approaches.

Field measurements provide the most accurate results and are indispensable for validating geospatial models. These methods can assess a wide range of soil quality parameters. While labour-intensive and limited to specific points in time, field measurements are highly effective for localized assessments. For CS, low-cost methods offer an easily applicable way

to contribute to monitoring efforts. However, chemical analyses require laboratory equipment and additional expertise.

4.11 RECREATION

Recreation is a vital component of cultural ecosystem services, offering opportunities for physical activity, relaxation, and connection with nature. These experiences enhance visitor well-being and foster a deeper appreciation for natural areas. Assessing the quantity and quality of recreational infrastructure, such as trails, accessibility features, and amenities, is essential for ensuring that these spaces meet the needs of diverse user groups.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

We have not found a suitable method for analysing recreational services using geospatial data, as freely available data often lack the necessary spatial resolution and provide no information on the quality of the infrastructure. For this, field assessments are required.

However, the project ResCulES [11] provides a manual for processing spatially explicit indicators on various recreational activities through Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to evaluate these ES. Unfortunately, the manual is only available in German. However, the framework is flexible and can be adapted for use in other countries, provided equivalent field-observation data are available and regional adjustments are made. Proficiency in GIS software is required to apply the method.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Both CS and scientists can evaluate the quantity and quality of recreational infrastructure by conducting field surveys and organizing the data into thematic layers using GIS. The approach is simple, cost-efficient, and produces reliable results. Although field surveys require no specialized training, analysing the data does require basic GIS skills. Online research prior to site visits, such as reviewing maps, visitor feedback, and accessibility details on park websites, can further aid in planning and data collection. Citizen scientists' contributions are particularly valuable because they can provide unique insights into visitor experiences and help identify overlooked issues, such as accessibility challenges or underutilized facilities. Their involvement also allows for the collection of diverse perspectives, which can complement professional assessments and support more inclusive park management strategies.

Field assessments are prone to local and temporal biases. Visitor numbers often fluctuate based on the day of the week, weather, or season, and food and beverage availability may also vary seasonally. To address these issues, repeated surveys are often necessary.

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

The quality of recreational infrastructure in wetlands can be best assessed through field measurements. Here, CS can help reduce the workload, increase the data quantity, and provide valuable insights from different perspectives. The findings can support local managers in identifying strengths and weaknesses in recreational offerings and guiding improvements to better meet visitor needs.

4.12 RESEARCH AND EDUCATION

Research and education are critical for fostering environmental awareness and promoting sustainable management of natural resources. Educational trails and interactive learning opportunities help people connect with nature, enhance their ecological literacy, and inspire them to take action to protect the environment.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

Like for recreational activities, we did not find any adequate methods for analysing educational services via geospatial data. However, information on educational trails can often be found online. Many national parks and nature reserves publish details about their trails, including the themes, learning opportunities, and target audiences. This information can serve as a starting point for researchers or educators interested in studying or developing educational trails.

However, it is important to note that online research has its limitations. Information may not always be complete, accurate, or up-to-date, particularly for smaller or less-frequently visited nature reserves. Researchers may need to verify details through direct communication with park authorities or on-site visits to ensure the reliability of the data.

2. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

For assessing the quantity and quality of educational activities, please see the methods described for recreational activities (chapter 4.11).

3. METHOD COMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Field surveys are the preferred approach for assessing the quality of educational offers as they provide reliable, highly accurate data. However, basic online research can serve as a helpful preliminary step to gain an initial overview of available options, such as identifying existing trails and their features. Both approaches are straightforward, do not require any prior training, and can be applied by both scientists and citizen scientists.

4.13 PLANT BIOMASS (MATERIAL)

Wetland plants can serve as valuable resources for various human needs, such as construction and fuel. While this chapter provides a method to assess the area of reed using geospatial analyses, the chapter "Global Climate Regulation" (chapter 4.4) includes both field-based and geospatial methods for evaluating biomass in trees, which can serve as indicator for timber and firewood production, or for herbaceous plants that could be used for construction or crafting material.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

Geospatial analyses allow experts to assess the area of reed using various spectral indices, such as NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index), NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), and WAVI (Water Adjusted Vegetation Index). This approach relies on freely available satellite data and offers medium accuracy. However, due to its complexity, it is recommended only for professionals. To assess the biomass per area, quantitative harvesting, drying, and weighing of plants is required.

4.14 PLANT BIOMASS (FOOD/FEED)

Wetland plants may support food security, local livelihoods, and ecological balance by contributing to sustainable agricultural systems and the survival of wildlife. Many wetland plants also hold cultural significance, further emphasizing their importance.

This toolbox offers approaches for assessing the provision of crops and plant biomass for human consumption and animal feed. This chapter focuses on geospatial analyses designed for experts.

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

The provision of arable crops for human consumption and grass for fodder can be assessed using geospatial analyses. Two indices, the Arable Crop Production Index (API) and the Plant Biomass Index (PBI), are specifically designed for this purpose, offering medium accuracy. Originally developed for the IDES tool [8], these indices are applicable in both active and former floodplain systems. They rely on existing, freely available data and require expertise in geographic information systems (GIS) for data processing. These methods are particularly useful for large-scale monitoring and for tracking changes in crop or plant biomass over time.

However, these approaches require access to soil maps indicating soil quality, as well as flood frequency maps, which are not always available in all countries. Additionally, the indices provide information only on the yield potential of existing agricultural land, rather than actual harvest data or the potential productivity of non-agricultural areas.

4.15 BIOMASS AND STOCKS (FOOD)

The provision of reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials, or energy in wetland ecosystems is essential for supporting food security, livelihoods, economic development, and sustainable resource use. Wetlands offer ideal conditions for aquaculture and the cultivation of aquatic species, which are important for human consumption, economic activities, and maintaining the ecological balance of these habitats.

This toolbox provides an approach for assessing commercial fishing yield. While this chapter focuses on reared aquatic animals for nutrition, the toolbox also includes a method for calculating the Commercial Hunting Index (CHI), which is based on the same principles as the index for commercial fishing (CFI).

1. GEOSPATIAL ANALYSES

The Commercial Fishing and Hunting indices (CFI/CHI) were originally developed for the IDES tool [8]. These methods rely on freely available data and provide comprehensible results on yield potential, with an expected medium level of accuracy.

Despite its utility, this approach has certain limitations. It depends on the availability of fishing/hunting statistics, which may not be accessible in all regions, and only accounts for economically utilized species. Additionally, while the method does not require advanced training, it demands expertise in geographic information systems (GIS).

4.16 PROVISION OF WATER

The provision of surface water in wetland ecosystems for nutrition, materials, or energy is critically important, as wetlands act as natural reservoirs of freshwater that support human needs, ecological processes, and biodiversity. Surface water from wetlands is essential for drinking, irrigation, industrial use, and energy production, while also sustaining the health and functionality of the ecosystems themselves.

This toolbox does not include specific indicators or methods exclusively dedicated to assessing the provision of water. Instead, the area, volume, and quality of surface water available for various uses can be evaluated using indicators from the ecosystem services "drought mitigation" (chapter 4.6), "flood mitigation" (chapter 4.7), and "water purification" (chapter 4.9). For example, drought mitigation indicators address water availability during dry periods, flood mitigation indicators assess water storage capacity, and water purification indicators evaluate the quality of surface water. These indicators can be assessed through geospatial analyses and field-based measurements, with methods suitable for both experts and citizen scientists.

5 FURTHER TOOLS AND METHODS

In addition to the provided toolbox, several collections of ES assessment methods exist. Some of them, such as the IDES tool and the InVEST software, are explicitly mentioned in this deliverable and have been applied in the Restore4Life project. Interested users can refer to the practical tools listed below to get further details on ES evaluations:

- **ValuES**

ValuES aims to support decision-making using ES by providing instruments and sharing knowledge. Among others, the Method Navigator is a practical tool to help choosing the right ES evaluation methods for specific situations.

[ValuES - Assessing Ecosystem Services](#)

- **RESI**

The manual on the **R**iver **E**cosystem **S**ervice Index (RESI) operates on a 5-level scoring system and was specifically designed to objectively assess ES in river-floodplain systems in Germany. The manual is in German language.

<https://repository.publisso.de/resource/frl:6410777>

- **IDES tool**

The IDES tool adapted RESI to the needs and data availability in the Danube River Basin. The tool extended the data-based assessment with participatory approaches and focuses on water-quality-related aspects.

<https://doi.org/10.17904/ku.edoc.30670>

- **InVEST®**

InVEST® is a suite of free, open-source software models used to map and value ecosystem services. It does not require knowledge of programming, but basic skills in GIS.

[InVEST | Natural Capital Project](#)

- **ARIES**

ARTificial Intelligence for **E**nvironment and **S**ustainability (ARIES) is an open-source-platform that uses cutting-edge technology, such as artificial intelligence for rapid ecosystem service assessment and valuation, among other environmental applications.

[ARIES - ARTificial Intelligence for Environment & Sustainability](#)

- **RAWES**

Using a field-sheet, Ramsar **R**apid **A**ssessment of **W**etland **E**cosystem **S**ervices (RAWES) is a practical tool for evaluating wetland benefits, designed to be simple, quick, and not reliant on detailed quantitative data.

[guide_rapid_assessment_ecosys_servs_e.pdf](#)

- **evaRest and ResCulES**

Specifically designed to comprehensively evaluate the effects of restoration measures on watercourses, evaRest (**e**valuation of **R**estoration) and ResCulES (evaluation of **R**estoration measures by **C**ultural **E**cosystem **S**ervices) were developed in Austria. The material is in German language.

<https://www.bmluk.gv.at/themen/wasser/gewaesserbewirtschaftung/leitfaeden/massnahmenevaluierung-fliessgewaessern-evarest-rescules.html>

- **BioAu**

BioAu aims to develop a practical biological method to assess the condition of floodplains. Material is available in German language.

[BioAu - Biozönotische Auenzustandsbewertung - Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung UFZ](#)

- **SELINA Project**

The Selina Project (**S**cience for **E**vidence-based and **S**ustainab**L**e Decisions about **N**atural Capital) aims to diagnose and test the capabilities of existing ES assessment approaches models, and indicators, among other tasks. <https://project-selina.eu/>

Deliverable 3.2: Derive a minimum set of key ecosystem condition indicators per ecosystem type

Deliverable 6.1: [Report on indicator review, selection and integration](#)

- **EWM**

The **E**uropean **W**etland **M**ap (EWM) is one of the most comprehensive data collections of the distribution and types of floodplains and wetlands in Europe and well suited for ES mapping in wetlands.

[The European Wetland Map](#)

REFERENCES

- [1] Stammel, B., Tschikof, M., & Cyffka, B. (2025). Ecosystem services along the Danube River and its floodplains: Uses, assessments, and their potential for policies and management. In *The Danube River and The Western Black Sea Coast* (pp. 321–334). Elsevier.
- [2] Mitsch, W. J., & Gosselink, J. G. (2015). *Wetlands*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [3] Ramsar Convention on Wetlands (2025) Global Wetland Outlook 2025: Valuing, conserving, restoring and financing wetlands. Gland, Switzerland: Secretariat of the Convention on Wetlands. DOI: 10.69556/GWO-2025-eng.
- [4] EEA, 2020. Report 24/2019: Floodplains: A Natural System to Preserve and Restore. European Environment Agency. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/floodplains-a-natural-system-to-preserve-and-restore>. Doi.org/10.2800/431107.
- [5] Jacob, L. M., Irvine, K. N., Beza, B. B., & Chua, L. H. (2025). Adaptive resilience in wetlands: An integrative review of principles, research gaps, and ways forward for better adaptive management. *Ecological Engineering*, 220, 107720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2025.107720>
- [6] Prasanya, J., Kanmani, S., & Senthil Kumar, P. (2024). A review of the wetland's restoration mechanisms and its economic and social benefits. *Water Practice & Technology*, 19(11), 4355–4377. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2024.241>
- [7] Haines-Young, R. and M.B. Potschin (2018): Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) V5.1 and Guidance on the Application of the Revised Structure. Available from www.cices.eu
- [8] Stäps, J., Gericke, A., Lungu, A., & Stammel, B. (2022). Ecosystem services in floodplains and their potential to improve water quality—a manual for the IDES Tool. <https://doi.org/10.17904/KU.EDOC.30670>
- [9] Mäder, P., Boho, D., Rzanny, M., Seeland, M., Wittich, H. C., Deggelmann, A., & Wäldchen, J. (2021). The flora incognita app—interactive plant species identification. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. 12: 1335– 1342. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13611>
- [10] Llodrà-Llabrés, J., Martínez-López, J., Postma, T., Pérez-Martínez, C., Alcaraz-Segura, D. (2023) Retrieving water chlorophyll-a concentration in inland waters from Sentinel-2 imagery: Review of operability, performance and ways forward. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 125, 103605. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2023.103605>
- [11] Hayes, D. S., Muhar, S., Popp, S., Becsi, R., Mühlmann, H., Ofenböck, G., & Scheickl, S. (2022). Evaluierung kultureller Ökosystemleistungen renaturierter Fließgewässer. *Österreichische Wasser-Und Abfallwirtschaft*, 74(11), 486–500. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00506-022-00895-0>

APPENDIX: FACT SHEETS

RGH1	Habitat Provisioning Index (IDES)	42
RHG2	Habitat/Species distribution modelling	44
RHG3	Habitat mapping using image classification	46
RHG4	Habitat configuration and connectivity	48
RHF1b	Water body mapping by Citizen Scientists	49
RPG2	Species detection using database queries	50
RPF1b	Native and invasive plant species by Citizen Scientists	52
RCG1	Land-cover-based C-stock assessments / InVEST model	53
RCG2	Above-ground C-stock estimates using LiDAR, spectral indices and elevation data	54
RCG3	Carbon stock and flux models based on EO data	55
RCF1	C-stock assessments using tree inventories	57
RCF2	Assessment of Carbon stocks in floodplain forests (tC/ha) by Citizen Scientists – Above- and below- ground biomass	58
RCF3	Weighing herbaceous biomass by Citizen Scientists	60
RCF4	Herbaceous biomass with the PhytoCalc method	61
RCF4a	Estimations of carbon stocks in soils with shallow organic layer by Citizen Scientists	62
RCF4b	Estimation of carbon stocks in peatlands by Citizen Scientists	63
RTG1	Regional temperature extremes using the Climpect heat wave index	64
RDG2	Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	65
RDG3	SWAT+ for assessing drought and flood events	67
RDF1	Soil moisture data loggers	69
RDF4	Water Level Measurements for Citizen Scientists with the CrowdWater App	70
RFG2	Water surface area (Spectral Indices)	72
RFG4	Flood Risk Regulation Index (IDES)	73
RFG3	Water volume (Bathymetric survey)	75
REG1	Sediment area	76
REG2	Sediment volume (LiDAR)	78
REF1	Sediment volume (field measurements)	80
RWG2	Nutrient Retention Index (IDES)	82
RWF1	Water quality index	83
RWF3	Water Quality by Citizen Scientists	85
CRF1	Potential for recreation by Citizen Scientists	86
CEF1	Assessment of educational activities by Citizen Scientists	87
RBG2	Reed area using spectral indices	88
PBG1	Crop and Biomass Provisioning Index (IDES)	89
PAG1	Fishing/hunting yields and quotas (IDES)	90

Habitat Provisioning Index (IDES)

Barbara Stammel (KUEI), Mathias Scholz (UFZ), Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	--	-------------------

Method description

All indices reflect the quantity and quality of floodplain-typical habitats for 1-10 km wide river-floodplain compartments on a 5-level scale. For a comprehensive evaluation on a large scale, the simple index HPI_{simple} is appropriate, for more detailed assessments the indices HPI_{detail} and HPI_{river} should be used.

HPI_{simple} (Scholz et al. 2012)

This index estimates the ecosystem service habitat provision on basin scale or where more detailed information is missing. It uses no explicit habitat or species data, but proxies, such as Natura 2000 areas or protected areas/habitats in non-EU countries, land use intensity, share of wetland habitats, backwater influence and the extent of the former floodplain.

HPI_{detail} (Fischer et al. 2019)

This index can be applied on local to national scale and provides a more detailed assessment of the functional and structural quality of floodplain-typical habitats. It considers the occurrence of habitat types which are generally assessed by their conservation and protection status, ground water and floodplain dependence, regenerability, and specific typical abiotic and biotic positive and negative characteristics, such as an altered flooding regime.

HPI_{river} (Nissl et al. 2020)

This index exclusively focuses on typical habitats of river channels and their closest banks. The variables are obtained from hydro-morphological (river structure mapping), biological and water quality assessments (from Water Framework Directive (WFD) monitoring). This index should be applied with detailed data on the local scale.

The method descriptions in English can be found in fact sheets in the IDES Manual (Stäps et al. 2022).

Strengths

- Harmonized assessments applicable in the Danube River Basin and EU member states
- Based on existing and freely available data
- No expert knowledge required, besides GIS skills
- Easy comprehensible results from 1-5

Limitations

- Exclusively for floodplains
- Does not replace monitoring, no local assessment at species level
- Evaluations of small-scale restoration measures on parts of the floodplain hardly possible
- Aggregated and simplified evaluation from 1-5

Recommendations & Comments

The three habitat provisioning indices evaluate floodplain and river habitats at larger scales, based on available indicators. They represent a useful screening tool to identify valuable wetlands, abiotic and anthropogenic constraints and potential restoration areas. However, the indices are too aggregated to evaluate the effect of local restoration measures affecting only small parts of the floodplain.

Sources

- Fischer, C., Damm, C., Foeckler, F., Gelhaus, M., Gerstner, L., Harris, R., Hoffmann, T.G., Iwanowski, J., Kasperidus, H.D., Mehl, D., Podschun, S.A., Rumm, A., Stammel, B. & Scholz, M. (2019). The "habitat provision" index for assessing floodplain biodiversity and restoration potential as an ecosystem service – Method and application. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 7, 483. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2019.00483>
- Nissl, M., Stammel, B., Lentz, A., Foeckler, F., Parzefall, C., Fischer-Bedtke, C., Damm C., Gelhaus, M., Gerstner, L., Kasperidus, H.D., Scholz, M. & Rumm, A. (2020). Quantifizierung und Bewertung der Ökosystemleistung Habitatbereitstellung im Fluss – AquaRESI. *UFZ-Bericht 2/2020*: 171 – 180. <https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=20939&ufzPublicationIdentifier=25854>
- Podschun, S., Albert, C., Costea, G., Damm, C., Dehnhardt, A., Fischer, C., Fischer, H., Foeckler, F., Gelhaus, M., Gerstner, L., Hartje, V., Hoffmann, T. G., Hornung, L., Iwanowski, J., Kasperidus, H., Linnemann, K., Mehl, D., Rayanov, M., Ritz, S., Rumm, A., Sander, A., Schmidt, M., Scholz, M., Schulz-Zunkel, C., Stammel, B., Thiele, J., Venohr, M., Haaren, C. von, Wildner, M. and Pusch, M. T. (2018), RESI-Anwendungshandbuch: Ökosystemleistungen von Flüssen und Auen erfassen und bewerten. <https://www.resi-project.info/handbuch/>
- Scholz, M., Mehl, D., Schulz-Zunkel C., Kasperidus, H.D., Born, W. & Henle, K. (2012). Ökosystemfunktionen von Flussauen. Analyse und Bewertung von Hochwasserretention, Nährstoffrückhalt, Kohlenstoffvorrat, Treibhausgasemissionen und Habitatfunktion.
- Stäps J., Gericke, A., Lungu A. Stammel, B. (2022). Ecosystem services in floodplains and their potential to improve water quality – a manual for the IDES Tool. <https://doi.org/10.17904/ku.edoc.30670>

Habitat/Species distribution modelling

Andrej Halabuk (ILESAS), Ľuboš Halada (ILESAS)

Accuracy 			
--	---	---	---

General approach

Understanding the potential distribution of species is crucial for effective nature conservation and management. Managers of protected areas often work with incomplete data on species occurrence. Habitat/Species Distribution Modelling (HSM/SDM) provides a powerful statistical tool to bridge these data gaps. By correlating known species' locations with environmental variables, these models can predict the suitability of habitats across a wider landscape. This allows for the creation of risk maps, aids in the design of restoration monitoring programs, and helps prioritize management actions.

Workflow

The process of creating a habitat suitability map involves predicting a species' potential distribution based on its relationship with environmental factors. The workflow is typically divided into three phases: i) Data preparation, where species occurrence and environmental data are collected, cleaned, and formatted ii) Model fitting and validation, where a statistical algorithm calculates the relationship between species presence and environmental conditions, and its predictive performance is rigorously tested iii) Prediction and interpretation, where the fitted model is used to project habitat suitability across the entire area of interest, resulting in a predictive map. User-friendly tools often guide the user through this entire workflow, from data input to the generation of final maps and evaluation statistics.

Required equipment

- Standard personal computer (PC) or laptop
- GPS handheld device (optional, for collecting own field data)

Required data

- **Species occurrence data:** This includes records of where the species has been found. The most common formats for these data are CSV files (a simple table with columns for species name, longitude, and latitude) or Shapefiles (.shp). The data can come in different types and from various sources:
- **Presence-only data:** The most common type, recording only where a species has been observed. Typical sources include large public databases (e.g., GBIF, iNaturalist), literature records, or dedicated citizen science campaigns.
- **Presence-absence data:** More valuable but rarer data that include both records of presence and locations that were systematically surveyed and where the species was confirmed to be absent. **Environmental data:** A set of raster maps (grids) representing different environmental factors. These can be conceptualized into two main groups:
- **Hydroclimatic variables:** such as temperature, precipitation, or variables derived from a digital elevation model (e.g., elevation, slope, topographical wetness index – TWI).

- **Landscape variables:** describing land cover, habitat structure, and human influence (e.g., distance from rivers, forest fragmentation). These data layers can either be created from remote sensing data (e.g., Sentinel-2 satellite data, orthophotos), or existing products can be used, such as the Copernicus High Resolution Layers (HRL).
- **Ground truthing data (optional):** Independently collected field data used for model validation.

Required software

- Spreadsheet software (e.g., MS Excel, LibreOffice Calc) for preparing species data.
- GIS mapping software (e.g., QGIS) for preparing and visualizing environmental data and final maps.
- Specialized, user-friendly modelling software such as MaxEnt or dedicated R packages for integrated approaches like IntSDM and specleanr for data cleaning.

Strengths

- Provides predictive maps of habitat suitability across large areas, effectively filling gaps in field survey data and identifying potential, yet unknown, locations of species occurrence.
- Enables targeted and cost-effective management by highlighting high-risk zones for invasion, thus helping to prioritize monitoring, control, and restoration efforts.

Limitations

- Model accuracy is highly dependent on the quality of input data; results can be misleading if occurrence data is spatially biased (e.g., collected only along roads).
- The output is a statistical prediction of suitability based on correlation, not a map of actual presence. Results always require expert interpretation and should be validated with field observations.
- The implementation needs some GIS/data processing knowledge with a dedicated training of professionals.

Recommendations & Comments

The approach is applicable at different spatial scales, from local site management to regional planning. Baseline predictors and selected occurrence data for chosen species from GBIF will be made available on the Restore4Life portal, which can serve as a starting point for analyses.

Sources

Mostert, P.S., Bjørkås, R., Bruls, A.J.H.M., Koch, W., Martin, E.C., Perrin, S.W., 2025. intSDM: An R Package for Building a Reproducible Workflow for the Field of Integrated Species Distribution Models. *Ecology and Evolution* 15.. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.71029>.

Habitat mapping using image classification

Dusanka Cvijanović (UNSPMF), Maja Novković (UNSPMF)

Accuracy 			
--	---	---	---

Method description

The presence and characteristics of aquatic vegetation (species abundance and stand area) and habitats are effectively assessed using UAV-based photogrammetry.

UAV-based geotagged images are adjusted and stitched into individual georeferenced orthomosaics. Orthomosaics are further processed using supervised object-based image classification (OBIA) to recognize and distinguish macrophyte functional groups, taxa, and habitats. The orthomosaic classification workflow includes three phases: i) orthomosaic segmentation and calculation of classification attributes ii) training and validation data sets creation iii) classification and reclassification. Classification attributes are calculated based on spectral characteristics and spatial distribution (spectral and texture indices). Training and validation data sets are created based on field ground truthing data and manual visual selection of appropriate segments by trained professionals.

Required equipment: UAVs with RGB (and preferably multispectral) camera; Ground control points (GCP) or GPS or GNSS handheld device

Required data: Geotagged images; GSP or GNSS data; Ground truthing data

Required software: MS Excel; GIS mapping software with image analysis modules (ArcGIS, QGIS, AgiSoft)

Strengths

- Cost-effective conservation and ecological screening of aquatic habitats along the great river floodplains
- High data resolution (if needed cm2 level data could be obtained)
- High modularity – method could be easily adjusted according to the assessment area characteristics
- High replicability – suitable for timeline series creation or monitoring purposes
- Low-cost technique once all needed equipment is purchased
- Non-invasive – low disturbance of the habitats and wildlife species present at the assessment area

Limitations

- Require high level of expertise (trained UAV pilot, advanced level of GIS software knowledge, basic knowledge of macrophyte species present at the assessment area).
- Require specific kinds of equipment
- In situation of large assessment areas (>50ha) requires data storage and processing plan
- Relies on the adequate weather conditions (sunny weather, without strong winds and precipitation)

Recommendations & Comments

If possible, use professional UAVs with RTRK module and combination of RGB and multispectral cameras. RTRK module enables precise GNSS positioning and high precision GIS products (orthomosaics, final maps, etc). Combined RGB and multispectral cameras enable simultaneous acquisition of both types of images and their parallel usage in further analyses without additional processing.

Sources

Cvijanović D, et al. (2025) Conservation and ecological screening of small water bodies in temperate riverine wetlands using UAV Photogrammetry (Middle Danube). *Nature Conservation* 58: 61–82.

Habitat configuration and connectivity

Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 			
--	---	--	---

Method description

Metrics for landscapes:

- The R-package '**landscapemetrics**' (Hesselbarth et al. 2019) is an open-source tool to analyse spatial patterns for categorical maps at patch, class, and landscape level. It calculates various landscape metrics related to area, shape, edge, diversity, and spatial configuration of landscape elements. It is an extensive collection of commonly used metrics, implementing metrics from '**Fragstats**' (<https://www.fragstats.org/>) and new ones from current literature that can be integrated into larger workflows.
- The R-package '**lconnect**' (Mestre and Silva 2023) is more specialized than 'landscapemetrics' for analyzing landscape connectivity and its effects on species. It provides functions to derive landscape connectivity metrics from vectoral data and includes an approach to assess individual patch contribution to the overall landscape connectivity.

Metrics for river networks:

- The R-package '**riverconn**' (Baldan et al. 2022) calculates indices for assessing riverscape fragmentation on catchment and reach scales. Riverconn conceptualizes the river network as a graph to derive connectivity indices that can account for structural (the network's physical setup) and functional connectivity (process- or biota-related).

Strengths

- Free and open-source
- Operate on various scales
- Can be linked to ecological data for conservation planning, population and landscape ecology

Limitations

- Not all tools account for functional connectivity
- Interpretations are complex for certain metrics
- Experience in R-coding required

Sources

Baldan, D., Cunillera-Montcusí, D., Funk, A., & Hein, T. (2022). Introducing 'riverconn': an R package to assess river connectivity indices. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 156, 105470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2022.105470>

Hesselbarth, M. H., Sciaini, M., With, K. A., Wiegand, K., & Nowosad, J. (2019). landscapemetrics: an open-source R tool to calculate landscape metrics. *Ecography*, 42(10), 1648–1657. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.04617>

Mestre, F., & Silva, B. (2023). lconnect R package: A versatile tool for evaluating landscape connectivity and prioritizing habitat patches in conservation research. *Ecological Modelling*, 484, 110489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2023.110489>

Water body mapping by Citizen Scientists

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen Science 	Costs €			
---	--	---	--	-------------------

<p>General approach Citizen Scientists determine the main hydromorphological and riparian characteristics, the usage of wetland water bodies, and the water quality.</p> <p>Required equipment: none</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and cheap method to identify water body types • No training necessary • Data over time yield information about water level fluctuations and intermittency 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only coarse typology possible
<p>Recommendations & Comments Describe size categories via examples, e.g. size of a football field, ... (see protocol)</p>	
<p>Sources Feldbacher, E., & Weigelhofer, G. (2025). Assessments of the Status of Water Bodies in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17371864</p>	

Species detection using database queries

Ute Susanne Kaden (UFZ)

Citizen science 				
---	--	---	--	---

General approach

iNaturalist is a global citizen science platform for recording biodiversity based on crowdsourced observations. Anyone, including citizens, students, hikers, and researchers, can contribute data by uploading georeferenced photos or sounds of organisms via the iNaturalist mobile app (iOS/Android) or website. Automated image recognition provides initial species suggestions, which are then reviewed by the global community.

Species data can be accessed in three ways:

- via the web interface, allowing filters (species, map area, time, quality, etc.) and export as CSV;
- via the API for programmatic queries (e.g., using `pyinaturalist`) with output in JSON format;
- via bulk datasets, which include weekly Darwin Core Archives of all research-grade observations and taxonomy, available through GBIF or AWS.

Required equipment and data

A GPS-enabled smartphone or digital camera with internet access. No scientific equipment is required. **iNaturalist** can be used via web, app, or scripts. For API use, basic programming knowledge and internet access are needed.

Strengths

- Large global biodiversity database
- Free and open access
- Easy to use with mobile app or web interface
- Suitable for data-poor regions for baseline biodiversity monitoring and citizen science projects
- Broad taxonomic coverage: plants, fungi, invertebrates, birds, mammals, amphibians, etc.

Limitations

- No standardized sampling method, risk of observations biased toward charismatic or visible species
- Geographical data bias (urban areas > remote regions)
- Risk of misidentification due to community-based input
- Difficult to use for cryptic or hard-to-identify species
- No restriction on taxa, but not ideal for systematic surveys (e.g., full inventory of all beetles in a 1m² plot)

Recommendations & Comments

iNaturalist is open-access and allows participation by non-experts and professionals alike. It is one of the most widely used biodiversity recording apps worldwide, particularly popular for plant, insect, bird, and fungus identification (2025: over 150 million observations contributed by more than 5 million users). **Projects** help structure sampling efforts (e.g., by region, taxa, timeframe).

Observations with date, location, and community agreement (minimum 2 users) reach **Research Grade** and are shared with the GBIF.

The web interface supports powerful filtering tools (e.g., taxon, location, date, photo/audio presence, quality grade, and project filters). Areas can be drawn on maps to restrict results. Data can be downloaded directly (CSV) or via the API (JSON), or accessed through GBIF bulk archives. Most data is shared under Creative Commons licenses (CC-BY, CC0, CC-BY-NC).

Sources

<https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/about>

<https://api.inaturalist.org/v1/docs/>

Van Horn, G., Mac Aodha, O., Song, Y., Cui, Y., Sun, C., Shepard, A., Adam, H., Perona, P., & Belongie, S. (2018). The iNaturalist Species Classification and Detection Dataset. In 2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. 2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR). IEEE.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/cvpr.2018.00914>

Native and invasive plant species by Citizen Scientists

Eva Feldbacher (BOKU), Clara Rosenberger (BOKU), Barbara Stammel (KUEI),
 Johanna Weidendorfer (KUEI), Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Costs €			
---	--	---	--	-------------------

General approach

CS identify 5–7 most frequent woody and/or non-woody plant species within a specific wetland area via an app. Additional data needed: Exact location of the area (GPS), size (e.g. 10x2 m), photograph, and estimated abundance. Additionally, the CS can add ecological indicator values for each species to get information about the ecological site characteristics.

Required equipment

Mobile phone with an app for plant species identification. Suggested apps: Flora Incognita (includes ecological indicator values, also offline), Pl@ntNet (also offline), iNaturalist, LeafSnap, Q-Plant, PictureThis, ObsIdentify

Optional: measuring tape or rope

Further detailed information on the identified species can be found at

<https://floraveg.eu/taxon/> (associated habitat, habitus, ecology, dispersal, etc.)

Strengths

- Many easy-to-use apps available for CS
- Some apps provide additional information about the plant for education
- If no internet is available in the field, some apps allow identification later based on taken photos
- Large data sets

Limitations

- Accuracy is highly variable, depending on picture quality
- Some apps need internet on site
- No full aerial coverage possible in cases where CS are not allowed to leave the paths

Recommendations & Comments

Define what the CS should determine (e.g., woody and non-woody plants). Provide details about how CS should select the study areas. Provide details and training on using the apps (e.g., pictures of different plant parts and angles, and check with auto-ecological data) to improve identification accuracy. Additionally, using multiple apps can improve identification, as each has its strengths and weaknesses.

Sources

Weigelhofer, G., Rosenberger, C., & Feldbacher, E. (2025). Assessment of plant indicator and invasive species in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Guideline and Protocols. In Horizon Europe Project Restore4Life (101112736). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17703928>

Land-cover-based C-stock assessments / InVEST model

Marie Wahl (BOKU), Maja Novković (UNSPMF), Dušanka Cvijanović (UNSPMF)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	--	-------------------

Method description

The carbon content stored in different land cover/land use (LCLU) types within a study site is estimated by applying the InVEST® model “Carbon Storage and Sequestration”. The model requires input data on four carbon pools (above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, soil carbon, and dead organic matter) for each LCLU class. The model calculates the total amount of carbon stored in these pools by aggregating the data according to land use maps and classifications provided by the user. The outputs are raster files with carbon values, which require further processing in GIS software and MS Excel to calculate total carbon stocks.

Required data and software:

- Land cover / land use maps (CORINE LC and/or Riparian Zones from Copernicus)
- Carbon pool values for at least one carbon pool (above-ground, below-ground, dead organic matter and/or soil organic carbon)
- Information on climate region and soil types
- Software: MS Excel, GIS mapping software, InVEST Workbench (<https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest>)

Strengths

- Straightforward workflow
- Versatility of the carbon pool data sources
- Allows comparison of carbon pools between different habitat types
- Allows prediction of future carbon sequestration potential of the area
- Allows overview of the past carbon storage pools of the area
- Enables coarse insight into carbon pools trends for the area

Limitations

- Depending on the expert knowledge about the assessment area
- The Riparian Zones model does not cover all target areas
- Corine Land Cover model could be coarse for complex ecosystems such as riparian wetlands
- Scarce info about specific habitat / vegetation type storage capacities in the literature

Recommendations & Comments

It is a prerequisite for the user to have basic knowledge in MS Excel and in GIS mapping software, like QGIS or ArcGIS.

Sources

Wahl, M. (2025). Assessing carbon stocks using the Invest Model - Guidelines and templates. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17371707>

Above-ground C-stock estimates using LiDAR, spectral indices and elevation data

Andrei Toma (GeoEcoMar)

Accuracy 			
--	---	---	---

<p>Method description</p> <p>This method estimates spatially continuous above-ground biomass (AGB) by integrating GEDI L4A footprint data with spectral indices from Landsat imagery and terrain information from SRTM DEM. A U-Net deep learning model is applied within a cloud-based workflow using Google Earth Engine and Google Colab.</p> <p>General approach</p> <p>Extract GEDI AGB points; compute spectral indices (EVI, NDMI, NDBI) and elevation from Landsat/SRTM in Google Earth Engine; sample GEDI points; train a U-Net model in Google Colab to predict biomass at scale.</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free & Global Data: Uses open-access GEDI, Landsat, and SRTM datasets. • Cloud-Based: Runs entirely in GEE and Colab, no powerful local hardware needed. • Deep Learning: U-Net captures spatial patterns effectively. • Flexible & Scalable: Adaptable to different regions and resolutions. • Multisource Integration: Combines spectral, structural, and topographic inputs. 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sparse GEDI Coverage: Footprints are not wall-to-wall. • Temporal Misalignment: GEDI and Landsat dates may not match perfectly. • Cloud Masking Limitations: Residual clouds can affect composites. • Generalization Risk: May not transfer well between forest types without retraining.
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>This method enables AGB mapping using only publicly available satellite data and computational tools.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Toma, A., Cvijanovic, D., Tschikof, M., & Scriciu, A. (2025). ABOVE-GROUND C-STOCK ESTIMATES USING LIDAR, SPECTRAL INDICES AND ELEVATION DATA. Restore4Life Protocol. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17703465</p>	

Carbon stock and flux models based on EO data

Marie Wahl (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	--	-------------------

<p>Method description</p> <p>Carbon stocks, carbon sequestration, and greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes in forests can be estimated using Earth Observation (EO) data.</p> <p>General approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon stocks Datasets from the ESA (Santoro & Cartus, 2024) or JRC (Avitabile, 2022) on forest above-ground biomass (AGB) are freely available and can be read in GIS mapping software. Data on the AGB of a predefined area can be extracted, and the carbon stock can be calculated as approximately 50% of the AGB (unit: Mg/ha). Carbon sequestration (change in carbon stock) ESA further published datasets on AGB change (unit: Mg/ha). These are maps that indicate the change of AGB from two consecutive years; negative values represent loss of AGB, and positive values represent gain of AGB. (Santoro & Cartus, 2024) GHG flux GHG fluxes can be calculated in an area of interest through the Global Forest Watch (GFW) map (Harris et al., 2021; Gibbs et al., 2025). In the tab "Climate" the Forest greenhouse gas emissions and net flux can be shown, the same as forest carbon removals. By either selecting a layer on the map, or manually drawing the area of interest, or uploading zipped shapefiles, forest-related GHG fluxes can be analyzed. <p>Required equipment and data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GIS mapping software Forest AGB/carbon maps: ESA CCI biomass map: map of global forest above-ground biomass (Mg/ha) at 100 m resolution. JRC forest biomass: map of the forest above-ground woody biomass stock (Mg/ha) of EU27 at 100 m resolution. GFW Climate (Forest GHG emissions, removal and net flux): global carbon flux at 30 m resolution (Interactive World Forest Map & Tree Cover Change Data GFW). 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low cost Open access Wide data coverage (EU27 to global) High spatial resolution (30mx30m and 100mx100m) Available for several years 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overestimation of biomass in areas with high biomass Underestimation of biomass in areas with low biomass Need for careful interpretation and should be validated with local data

Recommendations & Comments

The ESA also provides a product with related standard deviations of the AGB estimates (unit: Mg/ha) which should be considered when the AGB is calculated for an area of interest.

The map from the JRC is only available for the year 2020 and it was developed using advanced remote sensing data (e.g., ESA CCI biomass map) and was calibrated with ground-based reference statistics like the NFI.

Sources

Avitabile, Valerio (2022): Forest biomass map of EU27 for 2020. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/6d2cb333-7a81-4249-af30-18b2a91a8a90>

Gibbs, D. A., Rose, M., Grassi, G., Melo, J., Rossi, S., Heinrich, V., & Harris, N. L. 2025. Revised and updated geospatial monitoring of 21st century forest carbon fluxes. Earth System Science Data. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-1217-2025>

Harris, N.L., D.A. Gibbs, A. Baccini, R.A. Birdsey, S. de Bruin, M. Farina, L. Fatoyinbo, M.C. Hansen, M. Herold, R.A. Houghton, P.V. Potapov, D. Requena Suarez, R.M. Roman-Cuesta, S.S. Saatchi, C.M. Slay, S.A. Turubanova, A. Tyukavina. 2021. Global maps of twenty-first century forest carbon fluxes. Nature Climate Change. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00976-6>

Santoro, M.; Cartus, O. (2024): ESA Biomass Climate Change Initiative (Biomass_cci): Global datasets of forest above-ground biomass for the years 2010, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021, v5.01. NERC EDS Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, 22 August 2024. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5285/bf535053562141c6bb7ad831f5998d77>

C-stock assessments using tree inventories

Marie Wahl (BOKU), Krisztina Gulyás (EMVIZIG)

Accuracy 🔍🔍🔍	Expertise 💡	Time 🕒🕒	Costs €
<p>Method description</p> <p>Carbon stocks in forests can be estimated using local tree inventories. Forest inventories from official forest management units should include, at a minimum, data on tree species, age classes, area covered by each species, and yield per species or age class. This information allows for the calculation of the volume per species and/or age class. Using the wood densities of tree species, the aboveground biomass can be estimated, and the carbon stock can be calculated as approximately 50% of the biomass.</p> <p>Required data</p> <p>Local forest inventory and wood densities (e.g., from the Wood Density Database) Forest inventories can be requested at the local forest management units. For Hungary, the Hungarian Forestry Web Map is freely accessible (https://erdoterkep.nebih.gov.hu/) but only available in Hungarian language.</p>			
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High reliability of data quality • High accuracy • Low cost 		<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data usually not open access • No raw data • Potentially long data request times 	
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>Since detailed forest inventories often contain sensitive economic and private information, not all data may be shared publicly. It is likely that the information provided is aggregated or summarized to protect confidentiality.</p> <p>However, the Hungarian Forestry Web Map openly provides information on the size of the forest section, tree species, tree productivity, timber stock data, ownership, protection status, and more.</p> <p>Forest inventories may primarily focus on forest yields that are economically significant, such as timber volume, which means that the actual biomass in the forest could be 10%–15% higher than reported. However, this estimate should be verified with the local forest management units to ensure accuracy and account for any additional biomass components not included in the inventory.</p>			
<p>Sources</p> <p>Zanne, Amy E.; Lopez-Gonzalez, G.; Coomes, David A. et al. (2009). Data from: Towards a worldwide wood economics spectrum [Dataset]. Dryad. https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.234</p>			

Assessment of Carbon stocks in floodplain forests (tC/ha) by Citizen Scientists – Above- and below- ground biomass

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU), Eva Feldbacher (BOKU)

A) Tree height and circumference measurements in fixed area

Citizen Science 	Costs €			
<p>General approach Measurement of tree circumference at breast height and tree height with the triangle method, a clinometer or an app. Calculation of tree biomass and carbon stocks is done via easy formulas based on tree species and wood density.</p> <p>Required equipment: Measuring tape; stick or clinometer or tree height app</p>				
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to apply • Low costs 		<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree height estimates are difficult in dense forests, on uneven ground and slopes. • Tree height apps are prone to error if they are not used correctly and calibrated. • No possibility of CS to check correctness 		
<p>Recommendations & Comments We recommend the triangle method for measuring tree height. With little training, this method is more reliable than using apps and gives better results in the field. Also, using clinometers – if correctly trained – yield accurate data. Furthermore, we recommend recording the labelling of the measured trees to compare with other methods and detect the increment in biomass over time.</p>				
<p>Sources Weigelhofer, G., Wijffels, O., Rosenberger, C., Ramadan, H., Alphart, J., Novkovic, M., & Cvijanović, D. (2025). Assessments of Organic Carbon Stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists – Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328601</p>				

B) Angle-count sampling method for estimating forest stock volume

Citizen Science 	Costs €			
---	--	---	--	-------------------

<p>General approach</p> <p>The Angle Count Sampling (ACS), or Bitterlich sampling method, is a forest measurement technique used to determine the basal area of trees per hectare (m²/ha). Total tree biomass, and conversion into carbon stock is done with the help of easy formulas based on tree species and wood density.</p> <p>Required equipment: Bitterlich stick, relascope (easy to make by yourself); also possible with just your arm and thumb</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick and efficient • Minimal equipment needed • Works well for managed forests with homogenous tree structure 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires skilled/trained users • Tree height estimations still needed! • Not Ideal for small trees, deadwood, dense undergrowth
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>We recommend to train CS in the angle-count sampling method (ACS) as it can lead to large errors if used by untrained people.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Weigelhofer, G., Wijffels, O., Rosenberger, C., Ramadan, H., Alphart, J., Novkovic, M., & Cvijanović, D. (2025). Assessments of Organic Carbon Stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists – Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328601</p>	

Weighing herbaceous biomass by Citizen Scientists

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Costs €			
---	--	---	--	-------------------

General approach Estimation of plant biomass by harvesting and air-drying the plants.	
Required equipment: Device for cutting / harvesting the herbaceous plant layer (sickles, scythes, hand pruners, garden shears, machetes)	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and straightforward 	Limitations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destructive! (Not allowed in protected areas)
Recommendations & Comments If citizen scientists weigh the plant biomass, ensure that the balance is accurate enough! Refer the measurements to an area (e.g. per m ²). <u>Not recommended:</u> Herbaceous plant biomass provides only short-term carbon storage and will either be part of the soil organic stock or harvested; organic carbon estimates of the harvest will yield better results.	

Herbaceous biomass with the PhytoCalc method

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs
---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	------------------

General approach Estimation of plant biomass based on the mean shoot length and aerial coverage of homogenous vegetation types.	
Required equipment: aerial pictures, software/method PhytoCalc	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-destructive 	Limitations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coverage estimation difficult in the field • Calculation via factors from literature problematic if plant species are different
Recommendations & Comments Use computer programmes (e.g. Adobe) for estimation of aerial coverage. Model biomass equations for the most common vegetation types yourself for more accurate estimations of the factors. <u>Not recommended</u> due to (1) potentially high inaccuracies in the data, and (2) low relevance (herbaceous plant biomass provides only short-term carbon storage and will either be part of the soil organic stock or harvested; organic carbon estimates of the harvest will yield better results).	
Sources Bolte, A., Czajkowski, T., Bielefeldt, J., Wolff, B., & Heinrichs, S. (2009). Schätzung der oberirdischen Biomassevorräte des Baum- und Strauchunterwuchses in Wäldern auf der Basis von Vegetationsaufnahmen.	

Estimations of carbon stocks in soils with shallow organic layer by Citizen Scientists

Eva Feldbacher (BOKU), Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs € €
----------------------------	---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	---------------------

General approach

Characterization of soils by taking soil sample profiles, determining the depth of the organic layer, assessing texture, and analyzing the topsoil layer for soil moisture and organic content (ash-free dry mass).

Required equipment: shovel / soil sampler, measuring stick

Strengths

- Taking samples and determining texture is easy after short training
- Gives a good overview of soil structure

Limitations

- Determining sampling sites may be challenging for CS
- Needs a large number of soil samples
- Organic carbon amounts should be best analysed in the lab

Recommendations & Comments

Sampling can be done by CS if trained; the method of organic matter determination proposed in the protocols via the jar experiment does not separate OM from the mineral layers properly; CS could burn the soil at 300°C in their ovens, but we cannot recommend this procedure due to the danger of causing fire; besides, CS usually do not have balances precise enough to determine the small weight differences between dry weight and ash free dry weight; thus, we recommend to analyse the organic carbon in the lab. We cannot recommend using soil charts as people see colour very differently.

Sources

Weigelhofer, G., Wijffels, O., Rosenberger, C., Ramadan, H., Alphart, J., Novkovic, M., & Cvijanović, D. (2025). Assessments of Organic Carbon Stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists – Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328601>

Estimation of carbon stocks in peatlands by Citizen Scientists

Duškanka Cvijanović (UNSPMF), Eva Feldbacher (BOKU), Đurađ Milošević (FSM), Milica Stojković Piperac (FSM), Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Costs € €			
---	--	---	--	---------------------

General approach Estimation of peat depth and state of peat degradation (degree of humification).	
Required equipment: steel rods, measuring stick for peat depth	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to apply in the field by CS 	Limitations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CS trampling over sensitive peatland • Access restrictions in protected areas
Recommendations & Comments Not recommended for large groups but individual CS who are well-trained and instructed about nature protection measures. Organic matter can be easily determined by drying. The protocol also contains a link to a project which determines health and carbon sequestration in peatlands by using photographs.	
Sources Weigelhofer, G., Wijffels, O., Rosenberger, C., Ramadan, H., Alphart, J., Novkovic, M., & Cvijanović, D. (2025). Assessments of Organic Carbon Stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists – Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328601	

Regional temperature extremes using the Climpect heat wave index

Zorica Podračanin (UNSPMF), Biljana Basarin (UNSPMF), Dušanka Cvijanović (UNSPMF), Maja Novković (UNSPMF)

Accuracy 🔍🔍	Expertise 💡💡	Time 🕒🕒	Costs €
-----------------------	------------------------	-------------------	-------------------

Method description

The Climpect R package calculates climate extreme indices, providing information on the frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme temperature and precipitation events. The method is designed to transform raw meteorological data into standardized, comparable indicators relevant for multiple sectors such as agriculture, health, and water resource management. Indices are computed at monthly and annual scales, enabling easy trend analysis across different regions and time periods (Zhang et al., 2011).

Required equipment and data

Climpect uses quality-controlled daily minimum and maximum temperature data, as well as daily precipitation, to compute indices of climate extremes. The results help detect patterns and changes in extreme weather conditions relevant to wetland health and restoration assessment. The tool can be used either as an R package installed locally on a computer or via online platforms. Reference: <https://climpect-sci.org/>

Strengths

- Open-source and freely available tool.
- Standardized indices allow for comparison across regions and projects.
- Low-cost, requiring only existing meteorological data and basic computing.
- Well-suited for long-term climate trend analysis.

Limitations

- Results depend on the availability and quality of historical meteorological data.
- Indices are statistical – may not directly reflect ecological thresholds.
- The package cannot identify the specific days on which extreme events occurred; it only provides the frequency of extremes events within a year or month. This limitation may hinder more detailed analysis of individual events.
- Online use is limited to station-based data only, while spatial datasets require local installation on a computer.

Recommendations & Comments

Climpect is best applied in studies where long-term, quality-controlled weather station data is available. Its simplicity and standardized indices make it highly useful for both research and practical decision-making, especially for regional and site-specific trend assessments.

Sources

Zhang, X., Alexander, L., Hegerl, G. C., Jones, P., Tank, A. K., Peterson, T. C., Trewin, B., & Zwiers, F. W. (2011). Indices for monitoring changes in extremes based on daily temperature and precipitation data. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 2(6), 851–870. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.147>

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

Aleksandar Radošević (UNSPMF), Dušanka Cvijanović (UNSPMF), Milan Segedinac (UNSPMF), Maja Novković (UNSPMF)

Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs
---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	------------------

Method description

This system implements an end-to-end workflow for predicting environmental vegetation indices (such as NDVI, NDWI, and EVI) using machine learning.

The pipeline begins by **loading raw data** from Excel files. Data is parsed into structured entities representing daily environmental readings and vegetation indices.

Data preprocessing addresses missing values in the dataset through advanced interpolation techniques. Vegetation indices are imputed using linear, cubic, or spline interpolation. This results in continuous, gapless datasets suitable for machine learning, and this applies to the meteorological data as well.

For **model training**, the method employs a segmentation approach: sequences of previous 10, 20 or 30 historical day readings are transformed into feature vectors. This enables the modeling of temporal dependencies which is vital for accurate time series forecasting. Machine learning models are trained for each target index (e.g., NDVI).

Testing data undergoes the same transformations, and the trained models are then used to make predictions. Performance is evaluated using metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE) for testing/results data, and results—including predictions, expected outcomes, and performance statistics—are systematically stored for further analysis.

This modular approach fosters reproducibility and scalability. The structured storage of processed data and model results supports downstream analysis and visualization, providing a comprehensive platform for environmental monitoring and forecasting. The methods follow best practices in the field, as referenced in standard machine learning and time series literature (e.g., Géron, 2019; Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018).

Required data

Daily environmental measurements (in Excel or JSON format), including:

Air temperature, water temperature, precipitation (rainfall), water level, vegetation indices (NDVI, EVI, NDMI, NDWI, GNDVI, NDRE), temperature extremes (withing 85 and 90%)

Data should be structured with accurate timestamps for time series modeling.

Required software

Python 3 (recommended 3.8 or higher)

Required Python libraries: numpy, pandas, scipy, scikit-learn (for machine learning), openpyxl or xlrd (for Excel file parsing)

(Optional) Jupyter Notebook for exploratory analysis and reproducibility.

Other requirements

Sufficient disk space for storing datasets and intermediate files (in .json/.xlsx format).

Operating system: Any OS supporting Python (Linux, Windows, macOS)

Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Modular design allows for easy adaptation and extension to various indices and datasets• Fully open-source solution—no licensing costs• Well-suited for peatland monitoring and similar ecosystems• Handles missing data through robust interpolation methods• Useful for forecasting under different climate scenarios• Scalable to large regions and long-term datasets	Limitations <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Requires domain knowledge and technical skills for set-up and interpretation and not easily accessible for non-experts or citizen scientists• Initial data preparation and model training can be time-consuming• Accuracy relies heavily on completeness and quality of data• Limited support for real-time or streaming data without further development. (Can be expanded in future)
Recommendations & Comments <p>LSTM models offer a powerful way to analyze temporal trends in vegetation health or carbon-related variables. They require labeled training data and careful preprocessing but offer great potential when traditional modeling lacks flexibility or resolution. Integration with GIS for visualization and further interpretation is recommended.</p>	
Sources <p>Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. (2023). CORINE Land Cover [Dataset]. https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover</p> <p>ERA5. (2023). Climate Reanalysis Dataset. ECMWF. https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/</p> <p>Géron, A. (2019). <i>Hands-on machine learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow</i> (2nd ed.). O'Reilly Media.</p> <p>Hyndman, R. J., & Athanasopoulos, G. (2018). <i>Forecasting: principles and practice</i>. OTexts.</p>	

SWAT+ for assessing drought and flood events

Viktoria Arnold (BOKU), Bano Mehdi Schulz (BOKU), Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	---	-------------------

<p>Method description</p> <p>The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), and its latest version SWAT+, (https://swat.tamu.edu/) is a robust and highly flexible hydrological model designed to assess the impacts of land use, land management, and climate on the quantity and quality of surface and ground water (Wagner et al. 2022). SWAT+ operates on watershed-scale at a daily time-step. By dividing a watershed into smaller sub-basins and homogeneous hydrological response units (HRUs), the model allows for detailed spatio-temporal analyses of water flow, sediment transport, and nutrient cycling. It is also suited for assessing the impacts of wetlands such as floodplains on drought and flood events and evaluating the effects of landscape mitigation and restoration measures (e.g. Martinez-Martinez et al. 2014, Nauta et al. 2024). This makes it a valuable tool for policymakers, researchers, and environmental managers aiming to design sustainable water management strategies. A manual on how to implement natural water retention measures, including river and floodplain restoration, or wetland construction in the SWAT+ model, is summarized in Marval et al. (2022).</p> <p>In a case study, SWAT+ was calibrated and applied to part of the Austrian Morava River Basin, a tributary to the Danube, to simulate measures, such as implementing buffer strips, re-meandering rivers, altering land management practices, and constructing beaver dams (Arnold, 2025). The effects of the measures were evaluated on soil water content, low-flow and high-flow events over a 30-year period. The SWAT+ model integrates various datasets, including land cover, land use, soil properties, and climate data.</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free and open-source process-based model • Simulation of diverse land management, climate, and restoration scenarios, enabling users to test the effectiveness of various measures. • A high-resolution spatial and temporal analysis crucial for local decision-making. 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High complexity and extensive input data (e.g., land use, soil, and climate), which may not always be readily available or up to date. • Calibration and validation processes require expertise and can be time-consuming • Limited applicability to simulate hydraulic changes in stream and flooding extents during flood events, as compared to hydrodynamic models.
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>SWAT+ is a powerful tool for detailed assessment of wetland and catchment hydrology and requires a high level of expertise. In addition, SWAT+ can be used to model water quality and crop production, but it has certain limitations for assessing floodwater retention.</p>	

Sources

- Arnold, V. (2025). Einfluss von natürlichen Wasserrückhalte-Maßnahmen auf die Wasserspeicherung im March Teil-Einzugsgebiet (Master Thesis, BOKU University).
- Martinez-Martinez, E., Nejadhashemi, A. P., Woznicki, S. A., & Love, B. J. (2014). Modeling the hydrological significance of wetland restoration scenarios. *Journal of environmental management*, 133, 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.11.046>
- Marval, Š., Fučík, P., Čerkasova, N., Schürz, C., Strauch, M., Witing, F., Piniewski, M., Plunge, S., Farkas, C., Weiland, S., Krzeminska, D., & Lemann, T. (2022). SWAT+ and SWAP retention measure implementation handbook (D2.3 EU Horizon 2020 OPTAIN Project, Grant agreement No. 862756). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11232719>
- Nauta, S. M., Waterloo, M. J., Gevaert, A. I., de Bijl, J., & Brotherton, P. (2024). Micro-Catchments, Macro Effects: Natural Water Retention Measures in the Kylldal Catchment, Germany. *Water*, 16(5), 733. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16050733>
- Wagner, P. D., Bieger, K., Arnold, J. G., & Fohrer, N. (2022). Representation of hydrological processes in a rural lowland catchment in Northern Germany using SWAT and SWAT+. *Hydrological Processes*, 36(5), e14589. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.14589>
- SWAT+ Drought Tool on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16114248>

Soil moisture data loggers

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs € €
---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	---------------------

Method description

Use cheap and easy-to-install data loggers for soil moisture along hydrological gradients and in areas you expect to become wetter after restoration

Required equipment: Automatic soil loggers (optimal: remotely read out via mobile)

Strengths

- Continuous monitoring provides large amount of data
- High accuracy

Limitations

- Costs
- Damage due to flooding, etc.

Recommendations & Comments

We have had good experiences with TOMST data logger.

Water Level Measurements for Citizen Scientists with the CrowdWater App

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU), Georgia Arhire (UB), Mihai Cristian Adamescu (UB)

Citizen science 	Costs €			
---	--	---	--	-------------------

Method description

One of the most common methods of accurately measuring surface water levels or just to determine the rise/fall of the water surface over time is by using a graduated staff gauge attached to a static structure (e.g. a bridge, a dock, a steel rod driven down into firm ground), so that the water level readings are consistently taken to a fixed datum over time. Staff gauges are simple and reliable and used as reference sensors when calibrating electronic level sensors. Staff gauges are appropriate for water level measurement in rivers, lakes and also in wetlands, if secured firmly. A lot of staff gauges are already in place as part of the water-level monitoring network, but many flood-prone areas or small-scale streams are ungauged.

The CrowdWater App can be downloaded for free in Google Play and App Store and is available in several languages. Users can upload data for lakes (water level; type, description, and visible pollution of water body), rivers (type, temporary streams, water level, plastic pollution) and soil moisture. The App offers detailed guidance with pictures and is easy to handle. Data are open access.

Required equipment and data

Mobile device with GPS on and TheCrowdWater app installed

Strengths

- Created for Citizen Science, thus user-friendly, easy to handle, and fast
- No physical installations or sensors are needed
- Offline mode: Data can be entered and uploaded later if no internet is available
- Can be applied in remote areas and regions with low data availability
- Fun factor: Points are awarded for observations, and users can participate in a game

Limitations

- Only a restricted number of parameters can be observed
- Can be applied in remote areas and regions with low data availability

Recommendations & Comments

This app enables CS to record hydrological conditions and some descriptive parameters of water bodies. Of particular interest is the function of a virtual water gauge. If additional parameters are of interest, we recommend combining the app with an online or offline questionnaire, such as, e.g., the R4L water body mapping protocol.

Sources

Feldbacher, E., & Weigelhofer, G. (2025). Assessments of the Status of Water Bodies in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17371864>

Webpage: <https://crowdwater.ch/en/start/>

Manual: https://crowdwater.ch/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/SPOTTERON_MANUAL_CrowdWater_EN.pdf

Water surface area (Spectral Indices)

Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs €
---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-------------------

<p>Method description</p> <p>The water surface extent and its changes are important indicators of wetland health and water retention and are essential for monitoring large flood events and hydrologic reconnection measures, such as dike relocations. Water bodies strongly absorb light in the visible to infrared electromagnetic spectrum. Therefore, water surfaces can be easily detected by simple spectral indices, such as the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI). Spectral data and indicators can be obtained freely from satellite or aerial imagery of the Copernicus, Landsat and Modis missions or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). The Copernicus Browser provides a user-friendly interface to explore and assess spectral indices online (https://browser.dataspace.copernicus.eu/). NDWI uses green and near-infrared bands to highlight water bodies. For Sentinel 2 of the Copernicus mission, NDWI calculates as: $(B03 - B08) / (B03 + B08)$.</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NDWI: simple, robust and widely-used index • User-friendly, free, and worldwide application with the Copernicus Browser 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not work in areas with dense vegetation (forests) • Prone to cloud cover • Sensitive to built-up land, shadows, or snow which can result in over-estimation of water bodies
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>NDWI is the most widespread index for water detection and implemented as a standard product by many services. Other common and simple spectral indices helping detect open water areas include EWI, NWI, or WRI. The advantages and disadvantages in specific uses of these and various other indices are discussed in Zhao et al. (2025). To improve the mapping of water under vegetation cover, WIW (Water in Wetlands) has been developed. Another method to detect water bodies is using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data. SAR is better for all-weather, all-day monitoring, and for penetrating vegetation to find water bodies hidden from view (e.g. in wetlands), but it can be challenging to process and may blur boundaries.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Lefebvre, G., Davranche, A., Willm, L., Campagna, J., Redmond, L., Merle, C., ... & Poulin, B. (2019). Introducing WIW for detecting the presence of water in wetlands with landsat and sentinel satellites. <i>Remote sensing</i>, 11(19), 2210. https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11192210</p> <p>Zhao, C., Wei, H., Feyisa, G. L., de Castro Tayer, T., Ma, G., Wu, H., & Pan, Y. (2025). Evaluating spectral indices for water extraction: Limitations and contextual usage recommendations. <i>International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation</i>, 139, 104510. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2025.104510</p> <p>NDWI Scripts: NDWI Normalized Difference Water Index Sentinel Hub custom scripts</p> <p>WIW Script: https://custom-scripts.sentinel-hub.com/custom-scripts/sentinel-2/wiw_s2_script/</p>	

Flood Risk Regulation Index (IDES)

Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	--	-------------------

<p>General approach</p> <p>Flood risk regulation can be assessed by averaging two sub-indicators that refer to retained water volume and the slowing of flow velocity (Mehl et al. 2020, Stäps et al. 2022). The first sub-indicator is the ratio of the flood volume of the active floodplain to that of the former floodplain, indicating the remaining storage capacity of the floodplain. The second sub-indicator consists of the average value of hydro-morphological assessment scores for the river bed, river bank and riparian zone and is a proxy for the hydraulic roughness of the river corridor at high water level, affecting flood wave attenuation.</p> <p>Both sub-indicators are calculated and averaged according to the method provided in Stäps et al. (2022).</p> <p>Required equipment and data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital terrain or elevation model (DTM, DEM) • Hydro-morphological assessment classes (e.g. from Water Framework Directive reporting) • Land cover/land use data (e.g. Copernicus Riparian Zones or Corine Land Cover) • PC with GIS software (e.g. ArcGIS Pro, QGIS) and volume calculation tool 	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonized assessments applicable in the Danube River Basin and EU member states • Based on existing and freely available data • No higher training required, besides GIS skills • Easy comprehensible results from 1-5 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not replace hydrodynamic modelling for flood risk assessments • Aggregated and simplified evaluation from 1 –5 • Evaluations of small-scale restoration measures on parts of the floodplain hardly possible
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>The IDES Flood Risk Regulation Index is a very simple, but valuable screening tool to quickly assess the capacity of floodplains to reduce flood risk. It is recommended as an evaluation method for ecosystem services but should not be relied on in flood risk management. Furthermore, the index includes information on the ratio of active and former floodplain and thus holds information on the lost floodplain area having a certain reconnection potential. When DEMs are used for volume calculations, the water storage might be underestimated, particularly in forested floodplains.</p>	

Sources

Mehl, D., Hoffmann, T. G., Iwanowski, J. (2020). Quantifizierung und Bewertung regulativer Ökosystemleistungen: Rückhalt von Treibhausgasen / Kohlenstoffsequestrierung, Hochwasser-, Niedrigwasser- und Sedimentregulation, Bodenbildung in Auen sowie Kühlwirkung der Gewässer und terrestrischen Böden. In: Fischer-Bedtke, C., Fischer, H., Mehl, D., Podschun, S., Pusch, M., Stammel, B. & M. Scholz (Eds.). River Ecosystem Service Index (RESI) – Methoden zur Quantifizierung und Bewertung ausgewählter Ökosystemleistungen in Flüssen und Auen. UFZ-Report 2/2020, 77-92.

<https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=20939&ufzPublicationIdentifier=25846>

Stäps J., Gericke, A., Lungu A. Stammel, B. (2022). Ecosystem services in floodplains and their potential to improve water quality – a manual for the IDES Tool.

<https://doi.org/10.17904/ku.edoc.30670>

Water volume (Bathymetric survey)

Cristina Despina (INCDDD)

Accuracy 	Costs € € €		
--	---	---	-----------------------

<p>Method description</p> <p>The volume and hydrology of a water body is an indicator of its water storage capacity. Using an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) mounted on a motorboat and a GPS antenna, bathymetric surveys of the cross-sectional width, discharge, and flow velocities of water bodies, can be conducted. Depth data are part of the ADCP cross-sectional measurements, providing the basis for constructing bathymetric maps and for defining the geometry of the riverbed/lake bottom necessary for hydrological analyses and water volume estimations.</p> <p>Water level can be determined by integrating ADCP depth data with absolute water surface elevations. Combining surface elevation with depth measurements allows for the calculation of absolute bed levels.</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various hydrological data outputs with high accuracy 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very labour- and cost-intensive (High-end equipment needed)
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>On the Grădiştea-Bascealic monitoring site (Romania), bathymetric surveys were performed using an ADCP mounted on a float that was fixed upstream of the boat engine to reduce vibrations, propeller-induced currents, or wake effects.</p> <p>For discharge determination, a SonTek ADCP RiverSurveyor was employed. Water level was determined by two methods: (i) real-time kinematic (RTK) GNSS positioning with a Spectra Precision SP80 receiver, and (ii) readings from official hydrometric gauges.</p>	

Sediment area

Andrei Toma (GeoEcoMar), Albert Scriciu (GeoEcoMar)

Accuracy 			
--	---	--	---

Method description

Sediment gain/loss in inland waters areas can be assessed using waterbody boundary mapping through remote sensing (e.g., NDWI) combined with multi-date image classification. Area changes are tracked over time to detect sedimentation (shrinkage) or erosion (expansion).

General approach

Use satellite imagery to delineate waterbody extent using indices like NDWI or MNDWI. Compare waterbody footprints across time to identify sediment infills (reduction in area) or erosion (expansion). Validate with field or UAV data if possible.

Required equipment and data

- Satellite imagery (Sentinel-2, Landsat)
- Remote sensing software (e.g., Google Earth Engine, QGIS)
- NDWI/MNDWI index or classification methods
- Optional: UAV imagery or sonar depth data for validation

e.g. Image classification, Erosion/deposition

- Image classification (NDWI/MNDWI)
- Detect changes in waterbody boundary
- Sediment deposition = decrease in water area
- Erosion = increase in water area or boundary shift

Strengths

- Covers large areas consistently using freely available imagery (e.g., Landsat, Sentinel)
- Low-cost and accessible via platforms like Google Earth Engine or QGIS
- Moderate to high spatial resolution (10–30 m) suitable for lakes and rivers
- Enables multi-temporal analysis over decades for long-term trends
- No need for ground access, useful in remote or restricted areas
- Can be automated for repeated monitoring across seasons or years

Limitations

- May be affected by seasonal water level fluctuations, confusing real sediment change
- Cloud cover or shadows can obscure accurate shoreline detection
- Moderate resolution may miss fine-scale changes in small ponds or streams
- Vegetation or turbidity can interfere with waterbody classification
- Accuracy depends on quality of preprocessing and classification thresholds
- Requires technical expertise in GIS and remote sensing for proper analysis

Recommendations & Comments

Use multi-temporal satellite imagery with NDWI/MNDWI to monitor sediment-related changes in inland waters. Combine with field data or UAV surveys for validation. Recommended for low-cost, large-area, and long-term monitoring, but seasonal effects must be carefully considered.

Sources

Xu, H. (2006). Modification of normalised difference water index (NDWI) to enhance open water features in remotely sensed imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 27(14), 3025–3033. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160600589179>

European Space Agency (ESA). Sentinel-2 data. Retrieved from <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>

U.S. Geological Survey (USGS). Landsat satellite data. Retrieved from <https://landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

Google Earth Engine. (n.d.). Cloud-based geospatial analysis platform. <https://earthengine.google.com/>

Sediment volume (LiDAR)

Tudor Racoviceanu (UB), Marian Radu (UB), Mihai Cristian Adamescu (UB)

Accuracy 🔍🔍🔍	Expertise 💡💡💡	Time 🕒🕒🕒	Costs €€€
------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------	---------------------

Method description

Understanding the magnitude, spatial distribution, and temporal variability of sediment dynamics is essential for ecological restoration, hydrological modeling, habitat monitoring, and climate adaptation strategies. Particularly in dynamic or inaccessible landscapes like floodplains and wetlands, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors, have transformed how sediment monitoring is conducted. UAV-based LiDAR offers high-resolution, 3D structural data that can be captured rapidly, repeatedly, and non-invasively.

Equipment

- Drone (e.g. DJI Matrice 300 RTK)
- LiDAR module and camera (e.g. Zenmuse L1)

Workflow

Sediment volume estimation is based on digital elevation differencing:

- Two high-resolution Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) are generated before and after an event.
- By subtracting the pre-event from the post-event DTM, a raster of elevation change (ΔZ) is produced.
- The resulting raster highlights areas of erosion (negative ΔZ) and deposition (positive ΔZ) and can be used to calculate the volume (e.g. using CloudCompare's 2.5D volume tool)

Strengths

- High spatial resolution (cm-scale)
- Accurate 3D terrain data even in vegetated areas
- Scalable to large areas
- Well-suited for inaccessible or dynamic floodplain sites

Limitations

- High initial equipment and software costs
- Requires trained personnel for drone operation and data processing
- Data post-processing can be time-intensive
- Limited by weather and vegetation cover at time of flight

Recommendations & Comments

The protocol provides a robust, repeatable method for monitoring sediment dynamics in restoration projects. Accuracy depends on flight planning, measuring point density, and surface complexity. Corrections for vegetation, point density, and water levels may be necessary depending on site conditions. It is particularly valuable for detecting sedimentation or erosion after flood events or restoration interventions and for supporting hydrological and geomorphological modeling.

Sources

DJI. (2021). Zenmuse L1 Product Manual. DJI.

Turner, D., Lucieer, A., & Watson, C. (2012). An automated technique for generating georectified mosaics from ultra-high resolution UAV imagery, based on structure from motion (SfM) point clouds. *Remote Sensing*, 4(5), 1392–1410.

Toth, C. K., & Józków, G. (2016). Remote sensing platforms and sensors: A survey. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 115, 22–36.

Gonçalves, J. A., & Henriques, R. (2015). UAV photogrammetry for topographic monitoring of coastal areas. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 104, 101–111.

Hodgson, M. E., Jensen, J. R., Raber, G. T., & Tullis, J. A. (2003). Synergistic use of LiDAR and multispectral imagery for forest monitoring. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 84(4), 526–537.

Dietrich, J. T. (2016). Riverscape mapping with helicopter-based Structure from Motion. *Geomorphology*, 252, 144–157.

McKean, J., & Roering, J. (2004). Objective landslide detection and surface morphology mapping using high-resolution airborne laser altimetry. *Geomorphology*, 57(3–4), 331–351.

Passalacqua, P., Belmont, P., & Fofoula-Georgiou, E. (2012). Automatic geomorphic feature extraction from LiDAR in flat and engineered landscapes. *Water Resources Research*, 48(3).

Sediment volume (field measurements)

Valentin Dinu (UB), Mihai Cristian Adamescu (UB)

Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs
---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	------------------

General approach

Sediment volume in aquatic systems is commonly estimated by direct field sampling using sediment traps or corers. Sediment traps—often constructed from PVC tubes or trays—are deployed at predefined intervals to capture settling particles. Corers extract vertical sediment profiles that allow for the quantification of accumulated layers over time. In situ measurements of sediment thickness using graduated rods or subsequent lab-based volumetric calculations are performed. The collected sediments are typically dried and weighed to calculate bulk density, which, when multiplied by the thickness and area, provides a volume estimate. Additionally, grain size distribution through sieve analysis can be useful to determine the dominant particle size. For enhanced temporal resolution, repeated measurements over seasonal or event-driven timeframes are employed.

Required equipment

Sediment traps (PVC, Teflon, or custom-made, depending on system), corers (gravity, piston, freeze depending on sediment type), measuring rods or laser level for precise depth readings, GPS/GNSS equipment for high-resolution georeferencing, weighing scales (± 0.01 g precision), drying ovens (105°C standard for moisture removal), laboratory tools for porosity and grain size analysis (e.g., sieves, hydrometers).

Strengths

- Enables high spatial and temporal resolution in sediment deposition studies, especially in small basins.
- Inexpensive and accessible methods with minimal technological requirements.
- Suitable across diverse aquatic environments, from shallow wetlands to lakes and rivers.
- Effective for capturing short-term deposition events (e.g., floods, storms).
- Easily combinable with other data sources (e.g., remote sensing, ADCP profiling).

Limitations

- Laborious deployment and retrieval processes limit scalability in large or remote areas.
- Results are sensitive to hydrodynamic conditions and placement bias.
- Corers may disturb sediment stratigraphy if not used correctly.
- Sediment traps may underrepresent fine or resuspended particles.

Recommendations & Comments

Suitable for small to medium-scale studies where precise local measurements are needed. Regular maintenance and careful deployment of traps are essential for accurate results. Combined with remote sensing or modelling for large-scale estimates.

Sources

Cieśla, M., Bartoszek, L., & Gruca-Rokosz, R. (2019). *Effectiveness assessment of a new system of sediment trap in the investigation of matter sedimentation in a reservoir—A case study. Hydrology, 6(2), 48.*

Bloesch, J. (1980). A Critical Review of Sediment Trap Technique. *Aquatic Sciences, 42(1), 15–55.*

Keimowitz, A. R. (2016). Sediment Core Sectioning and Extraction of Pore Waters under Anoxic Conditions. *Journal of Visualized Experiments, (109), e53655*

Nutrient Retention Index (IDES)

Ute Susanne Kaden (UFZ), Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	--	-------------------

<p>Method description</p> <p>The index assesses the nitrogen and phosphorus retention capacity of a river–floodplain section (in kg ha⁻¹yr⁻¹).</p> <p>Data required: For nitrogen, the index N_{ret} reflects removal through denitrification. The controlling factors for N_{ret} are the hydraulic load and temperature in the river and soil characteristics in the floodplain (Tschikof et al 2022). For phosphorus, P_{ret} reflects retention through deposition. The controlling factors for P_{ret} are the hydraulic load in the river and the hydraulic roughness in the floodplain (Schulz–Zunkel et al. 2021). The detailed method description can be found in the IDES Manual (Stäps et al. 2022).</p> <p>A proxy–approach to reliably assess nitrogen retention based on denitrification is available (Kaden et al. 2023). This approach is tailored to German data sets, but likely applicable beyond, if information on the land use, soil types, soil pH and floodplain status is provided.</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applicable in the Danube River Basin and EU member states • Based on existing and freely available data • Evaluations of large–scale restoration measures possible 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusively for floodplains • Higher training required • Labour intense
<p>Sources</p> <p>Stäps J., Gericke, A., Lungu A. Stammel, B. (2022). Ecosystem services in floodplains and their potential to improve water quality – a manual for the IDES Tool. https://doi.org/10.17904/ku.edoc.30670</p> <p>Schulz–Zunkel et al. (2021). Simple modelling for a large–scale assessment of total phosphorus retention in the floodplains of large rivers. <i>Wetlands</i>, 41(6), 68. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-021-01458-x</p> <p>Tschikof et al. (2022). The potential of large floodplains to remove nitrate in river basins – the Danube case. <i>Sci. Total Environ.</i> 843, 156879. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.Scitotenv.2022.156879</p> <p>Kaden et al (2023) Improving an existing proxy–based approach for floodplain denitrification assessment to facilitate decision making on restoration. <i>Sci. Total Environ.</i> 892, 164727. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164727</p>	

Water quality index

Cristina Despina (INCDDD)

Accuracy

Expertise

Time

Costs

Method description

The Water Quality Index (WQI) is a very useful and efficient method for assessing (drinking) quality of water bodies. It is a dimensionless index, combining several water quality parameters into a single number, which is then assigned to quality classes. Chidiac et al. (2023) summarized a collection of commonly used water quality indices and their applications.

For example, the weighted arithmetic WQI method can be used, applying the following equation:

$$WQI = \frac{\sum Wi qi}{\sum Wi}$$
 where: qi is quality rating for each parameter i ; Wi is a weighting factor that measures the importance of a parameter in calculating the WQI. Qi is calculated according to the following equation:

$$qi = 100 \times \frac{Vi - VO}{Si - VO}$$
 where: Vi represents the observed value of the analyzed parameter; VO represents the ideal value of that parameter (it is 0 for all parameters, except for pH where it is 7 and DO 14.6 mg/L). Si is the standard permissible value of the parameter (table 1). The Wi factor is calculated using the following equation:

$$Wi = \frac{K}{Si}$$
 where: K is a constant that is calculated by applying the formula:

$$K = \frac{1}{\sum (\frac{1}{Si})}$$

Table 1. The maximum allowable concentration of the indicators monitored according to ord. 161/2006 regarding the II quality class, respectively the V quality class for TN and TP.

Indicator (unit of measurement)	Maximum permissible concentration (Si)
pH (pH units)	8.2
DO (mg/L)	> 7
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/L)	0.8
N-NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	3
N-NO ₂ ⁻ (mg/L)	0.03
TP (mg/L)	0.1
TN (mg/L)	1.5
P-PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	0.2
Pb (µg/L)	10
Zn (µg/L)	200
Cu (µg/L)	30
Cr (µg/L)	50
Ni (µg/L)	25

Depending on the value obtained for the WQI, the quality class to which the analyzed water body belongs is established (Table 2).

Table 2. Classification of water bodies according to the WQI method.

WQI numeric value	Quality Class
0-25	Excellent (I)
26-50	Good (II)
51-75	Weak (III)
76-100	Very weak (IV)
>100	Non-potable (V)

Strengths

- WQI offer an overview of water quality
- A method to simplify the complex water quality data into a single number
- An effective tool to monitor changes in water quality over time and space

Limitations

- To obtain comprehensive results, a large set of water quality parameters must be investigated
- Depending on the WQI, specific laboratory equipment and probes are necessary
- Issues related to input parameter selection and weighting, calculation methods, rating ranges

Recommendations & Comments

WQIs have been successfully applied in the lower Danube (Iticescu et al. 2013, Calmuc et al. 2020). In the Restore4Life implementation site IS4 (Enisala, Romania), the WQI was calculated for the years 2022–2024 , during spring, summer and autumn. Water samples were collected and analyzed from 5 sampling points.

The selected parameters in Table 1 were analyzed by *in situ* laboratory measurements. *In situ* measurements using a high-precision multiparameter YSI EXO2 were performed for several parameters, such as pH and DO.

Concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus fractions in the surface waters, were analysed using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 650 Spectrophotometer. The analytical method used for the analysis of heavy metals was inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS).

Sources

Iticescu, C., Georgescu, L. P., & Topa, C. M. (2013). Assessing the Danube water quality index in the city of Galati, Romania. [Carpathian Journal of Earth and Environmental Sciences, 8 \(4\), 155-164](#)

Calmuc, M., Calmuc, V., Arseni, M., Topa, C., Timofti, M., Georgescu, L. P., & Iticescu, C. (2020). A Comparative Approach to a Series of Physico-Chemical Quality Indices Used in Assessing Water Quality in the Lower Danube. *Water, 12*(11), 3239. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12113239>

Chidiac, S., El Najjar, P., Ouaini, N. et al. A comprehensive review of water quality indices (WQIs): history, models, attempts and perspectives. *Rev Environ Sci Biotechnol 22*, 349–395 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-023-09650-7>

Water Quality by Citizen Scientists

Eva Feldbacher (BOKU), Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Costs € €			
---	--	---	--	---------------------

<p>General approach</p> <p>For a reliable estimation of the water quality by citizen scientists, we recommend a combination of the following methods:</p> <p>Mini Secchi/transparency tube: A portable water clarity testing tool used to measure turbidity by determining the depth at which a black and white disc becomes invisible. Transparency tubes are suitable for shallow waters, turbid waters, and running waters.</p> <p>Water smell and colour description: Use standardized scales to classify the colour of natural waters and relate it to selected water quality aspects.</p> <p>Water quality test kits: Use simple test kits for determining nutrient levels (mainly N, P) and dissolved oxygen in water using colour changes or titration. The accuracy of the reading can be improved, and results can be published with specific apps (e.g. Deltares Aquality).</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secchi tube can be constructed at low cost. • Water quality test kits are easy to handle, also in the field. 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour determination is very coarse and subjective, plus depends on daylight intensity. • Water quality test kits enable only coarse estimation of the real values and are quite expensive
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>We cannot recommend using available apps for water colour (e.g. Eye on Water App or Mini Secchi App) as they require water bodies that are deep enough so that the bottom cannot be seen anymore.</p> <p>Attention with water quality test kits: The concentration range, which can be measured with the kit, should suit to the actual concentration range of your waters. At lower concentrations, tests kits, such as nitrate indicator strips tend to be inaccurate.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Feldbacher, E., & Weigelhofer, G. (2025). Assessments of the Status of Water Bodies in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Guideline and Protocols. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17371864</p> <p>Deltares Aquality: https://www.deltares.nl/en/software-and-data/products/aquality-app</p>	

Potential for recreation by Citizen Scientists

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Accuracy 	Expertise 	Time 	Costs €
----------------------------	---------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-------------------

<p>General approach CS determine the quantity and quality of infrastructure for certain recreational activities via questionnaires, such as opportunities for hiking, biking, swimming, and other recreational activities, as well as options for food and beverages.</p> <p>Required equipment: None required</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and accurate, provides a good overview about the offer of recreational activities 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be locally and temporarily biased
<p>Recommendations & Comments CS should report the locations/paths they used during the assessments.</p>	
<p>Sources Rosenberger, C., Feldbacher, E., Boitel, A., Chevallier, N., & Weigelhofer, G. (2025). Assessments of Recreation and Education Services in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328583</p>	

Assessment of educational activities by Citizen Scientists

Gabriele Weigelhofer (BOKU)

Citizen science 	Costs €			
---	--	---	--	-------------------

<p>General approach CS determine the quantity and quality of educational trails and information boards via questionnaires.</p> <p>Required equipment: None required</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy and accurate, provides a good overview about the educational infrastructure offered 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be locally and temporarily biased
<p>Recommendations & Comments CS should report the locations/paths they used during the assessments.</p>	
<p>Sources Rosenberger, C., Feldbacher, E., Boitel, A., Chevallier, N., & Weigelhofer, G. (2025). Assessments of Recreation and Education Services in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328583</p>	

Reed area using spectral indices

Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 🔍🔍	Expertise 💡💡💡	Time 🕒🕒🕒	Costs €
-----------------------	-------------------------	--------------------	-------------------

<p>Method description</p> <p>Reed is a valuable and widely available resource from wetlands, which is used as construction material (e.g. roofing) and other reed-based products (e.g. soil improver, reed-straws, etc.). Measuring the extent of reed beds is crucial to evaluate their market potential and environmental impact but is no simple task.</p> <p>Using thresholding techniques on spectral indices such as Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Water Adjusted Vegetation Index (WAVI), Tiškus et al. (2023) classified reed beds and assessed their extent using freely available Sentinel 2 satellite data.</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on public Sentinel 2 multispectral satellite data 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Method only for professionals
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>In addition to the mere extent, methods for biomass estimates in this deliverable could be used to assess reed stocks.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Tiškus, E., Vaičiūtė, D., Bučas, M., & Gintauskas, J. (2023). Evaluation of common reed (<i>Phragmites australis</i>) bed changes in the context of management using earth observation and automatic threshold. <i>European Journal of Remote Sensing</i>, 56(1), 2161070. https://doi.org/10.1080/22797254.2022.2161070</p>	

Crop and Biomass Provisioning Index (IDES)

Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 	Costs €		
--	---	--	-------------------

<p>General approach</p> <p>The provision of arable crops for human consumption and grass for fodder are important ecosystem services (ES) provided by fertile wetland soils. These provisioning ES also indicate human pressures on wetland ecosystems and are therefore crucial factors for management decisions. With the Arable Crop Production Index (API) and the Plant Biomass Index (PBI), the usable yield can be estimated (Denhardt et al. 2020, Stäps et al. 2022). Both indices are based on the proportion of arable land or grassland in a wetland and its yield potential. In active floodplains, a flood-induced yield loss is considered.</p> <p>Required equipment and data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land cover/land use data (e.g. Copernicus Riparian Zones or Corine Land Cover) • Flood maps (of frequent intervals less than 100 years) • Soil maps (soil quality assessment) • PC with GIS software (e.g. ArcGIS Pro, QGIS) <p>The detailed calculation procedures of API and PBI are provided in Stäps et al. (2022).</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonized assessments applicable in the Danube River Basin and EU member states • Based on existing and freely available data • No higher training required, besides GIS skills • Easy comprehensible results from 1-5 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not all countries provide detailed soil quality and flood frequency maps • Provides the yield potential on existing land, not the actual harvest or the potential in non-agricultural areas.
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>The IDES Crop and Biomass Provisioning Indices are quick and robust screening tools to assess both the current value for food production and a cause for wetland degradation.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Denhardt, A., Rayanov, M., Hartje, V., Sander, A., Horlitz, T. Benner, T. (2020). Quantifizierung und Bewertung versorgender Ökosystemleistungen. In: Fischer-Bedtke, C., Fischer, H., Mehl, D., Podschun, S., Pusch, M., Stammel, B. & M.Scholz (eds.). River Ecosystem Service Index (RESI) – Methoden zur Quantifizierung und Bewertung ausgewählter Ökosystemleistungen in Flüssen und Auen. UFZ-Bericht 2/2020: 59–76. https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=20939&ufzPublicationIdentifier=25846</p> <p>Stäps J., Gericke, A., Lungu A. Stammel, B. (2022). Ecosystem services in floodplains and their potential to improve water quality – a manual for the IDES Tool. https://doi.org/10.17904/ku.edoc.30670</p>	

Fishing/hunting yields and quotas (IDES)

Martin Tschikof (BOKU)

Accuracy 🔍🔍	Expertise 💡💡	Time 🕒🕒	Costs €
-----------------------	------------------------	-------------------	-------------------

<p>General approach</p> <p>The provision of animal protein for human consumption is an important ecosystem service (ES) and a livelihood for humans provided by aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. The Commercial Fishing and Hunting Indices (CFI, CHI) use available statistics of harvests and a spatial reference to estimate food availability from wild animals. Both weight (e.g. tons of fish) and the number of individuals (e.g. number of deer) can be used.</p> <p>Required equipment and data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fishing (CFI): length of the river section; Hunting (CHI): area of the hunting grounds • Statistics on the average annual commercial fishing/hunting yield OR normative acts with total allowable catch (TAC) / quotas • PC with GIS software (e.g. ArcGIS Pro, QGIS) <p>The detailed calculation procedures of CFI and CHI are provided in Stäps et al. (2022).</p>	
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No higher training required, besides basic GIS skills • Easy comprehensible results from 1-5 • If available, data are generally free • Provides the yield potential (TAC, quotas), and/or the actual harvest 	<p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on fishing/hunting statistics are often unavailable • Legal restrictions for commercial fishing/ hunting may exist • Does only consider economically used species
<p>Recommendations & Comments</p> <p>The IDES CFI and CHI are useful to estimate the current value for food production. However, the availability of data related to fish catches / game harvests might be restricted in some regions. Fishing or hunting for recreational purposes are not covered in this fact sheet.</p>	
<p>Sources</p> <p>Stäps J., Gericke, A., Lungu A. Stammel, B. (2022). Ecosystem services in floodplains and their potential to improve water quality – a manual for the IDES Tool. https://doi.org/10.17904/ku.edoc.30670</p>	

